

D 6.1 Synthesis Report on gender bias in each core-RFO and experimental results

D 6.1.

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Part A of D 6.1:

Practices in Panels – Synthesis report of five case studies in European research funding organisations

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ABSTRACT

This synthesis report draws on five case studies in five European research funding organisations (RFOs). We studied how review panels, as key actors in the research assessment process, work in practice. We were interested in the way panels act when they process, evaluate, rate and rank funding applications, and which gender dynamics and gendered practices become visible there. A further focus was on the composition of panels, how they are chaired and which function they have in the overall assessment process.

The study of practices in panels needs to take the heterogeneity of panels into account: Panels – also called boards, expert groups or councils – are embedded in very different organisational settings, formal decision-making in panels varies between RFOs, and RFOs have different levels of gender awareness and formal gender policies in place. This heterogeneity becomes relevant when panels apply criteria and negotiate what is considered as an excellent application. To identify potential risks for gender bias we identified different types of practices: gendered and explicitly gender-related practices, and seemingly gender-neutral practices which may have gendered outcomes. Based on these findings we discuss some broader challenges for panels and RFOs, aiming for a (gender-)fair research assessment. These are linked to the concept of excellence and a more intersectional approach as well as to re-ranking policies which strive for gender-balanced funding outcomes. Finally, we discuss how RFOs can organise, facilitate and support the implementation of formal, in particular innovative, (gender equality) policies in practice.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CoI	Conflict of Interest
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EC	European Commission
ERC	European Research Council
FFP	Frontiers for the Future Programme
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
GC	General Call
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GiRI	Gender in Research and Innovation
IC	Informed Consent
IPD	International postdoc grant
MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NCN	Narodowe Centrum Nauki (National Science Centre Poland)
PI	Principal investigator
RFO	Research funding organisation
SFI	Science Foundation Ireland
SRC	Swedish Research Council
SRDA	Slovak Research and Development Agency
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

While policies of selected research funding organisations (RFOs) as well as potential risks for gender bias across their funding processes and in selected funding instruments were analysed in D5.1. (Husu and Peterson 2022), in this report the focus shifts from policies to their implementation and practices, and zeroes in on a key phase of the funding process: panel work.

This deliverable reports on the work conducted in GRANteD WP 6, Task 6.1 (Interviews with RFO staff) and Task 6.2 (Interviews with peer reviewers and/or panel members or observations).

Among others, the main questions this deliverable addresses are: How are the panels¹ structured, chaired and composed, and how are they instructed and monitored? How are the funding applications processed, evaluated, rated and ranked in the panels, and what kind of gender dynamics and gendered practices can be identified in the panel work?

Here, we refer to the concept of ‘practices’ as “the way in which activities are performed in organisations” (Poggio 2006, 225). They are socially constructed by the various actors involved, based on their individual preferences, experiences and cultural background. It is important to underline that there are different types of practices that are relevant in our analysis: gendered and explicitly gender-related practices, and seemingly gender-neutral practices which may have gendered² outcomes. Some practices can have biased and unfair outcomes which are not primarily gendered.

Practices in panels were studied in consideration of their heterogeneity: Firstly, panels are embedded in various organisational settings; secondly, their function in the assessment process and formal decision-making in panels varies between RFOs; and, finally, the level of gender awareness differs among RFOs.

This synthesis report draws on five case studies conducted in five European RFOs in five countries. In each RFO, one funding instrument was selected for a more detailed analysis. Findings from studying practices in the panels of these five instruments for assessing and processing applications are presented in this report.

The report is structured as follows: After some methodological remarks including data and research questions in chapter 2, we discuss the contexts of panel work in chapter 3. In chapter 4, the focus is on practices in more detail, before some overall issues related to panel work are discussed in chapter 5.

¹ A ‘panel’ in the five RFOs in the focus of this deliverable is considered as an advising body to the RFOs and their councils/boards, which has the ultimate responsibility for making decisions on account of the organisation. In most RFOs panels assist the decision-making body with expert advice on which applications to fund. However, the members of the panel themselves, of course, have to come to a decision on which applications they advise to be funded. In one of the assessed RFOs, the panel itself decides on funding. Not all five RFOs refer to this body as “panel”: In one RFO, it is called a “board” (FWF), in another “council” (SRDA) and in yet another “expert group” (NCN). To avoid confusion and to increase readability, we only use the term “panel” for the advising/deciding body as analytical entity. Members of panels are called panel members or panellists, while remote reviewers conduct their work individually, without a group/panel.

² We use ‘gender’ when referring to the socially constructed identity (not to a binary, female/male distinction).

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research background

The design of the case studies builds on the GRANteD conceptual framework (D2.1) (van den Besselaar and Mom 2020) and the dimensions pointed out there as relevant for studying practices in review panels. It also draws on the GRANteD literature review D1.1 (Cruz Castro and Sanz Menéndez 2019), which addressed relevant aspects when studying potential gender bias in peer review panels.

In the following, the most important aspects guiding our analysis are briefly presented.

The **composition of the panel** in respect to the share of female and male members has been pointed out in the literature as a relevant area. Panel members can be seen as gatekeepers who control access to funding resources (Merton 1973, Husu 2004; Husu and de Cheveigné 2010). Accordingly, and in line with the ERA target, many RFOs have implemented a target quota for female panel members (and some also for female remote reviewers) or a gender balance target. However, research is not in agreement about the gendered effects of these policies on funding outcomes: Some studies on recruitment processes have found that female applicants benefit from the presence or a higher percentage of female reviewers (Cheechi et al. 2019). Also, Van den Brink et al. (2006) found a positive correlation between the success of female candidates applying for university professorships in the Netherlands and the number of women in committees. Other studies found that a higher share of women in panels did not increase the share of women selected, and female reviewers did not notably favour female candidates (Bagues et al. 2017). In their analysis of Austrian FWF data sets, Mutz et al. (2015) and Marsh et al. (2011) found no evidence for a correlation in respect to the funding outcome of female applicants when the reviewers were female as well.

Scientific excellence and the (quality of) criteria applied to measure excellence have been widely discussed in respect to potential bias, also gender bias. Gender scholars have highlighted various suboptimal aspects of discussing and assessing excellence in review panels, referring to the way how excellence is defined, but also how this formal criterion is applied in the context of various panels. Heilman (2001) showed that the more ambiguous assessment criteria are, the more they open up room for individual interpretations and stereotypes (cf. also Carli 2016). For example, a vague definition of independence – a criterion highly relevant when assessing early career researchers – showed some gendered effects and challenges in the assessment of this indicator (Schiffbänker et.al. 2022).

Even if criteria are well-defined, they can be used in a manner that is not gender-neutral (Van den Brink and Benschop 2012). What is perceived and assessed as excellent mostly refers to the reviewer's own standards and interpretation of excellence; other applicants are compared to one's own career standards (Bird 1996) and stereotypes. Identifying gender stereotypes as one core source for bias might become manifest in the written reports of reviewers³.

³ Please note that the analysis of stereotypical language in review reports and applications is not part of this deliverable, but is analysed in deliverable D6.2.

The request to take gender into account in the design of research projects and in the analysis and interpretation of data adds a new layer to the assessment of excellence (Fritch et al 2022).

As early as in 2001, Heilman pointed to the impact of a lack of structure in **decision-making processes** of assessment bodies. This lack might lead to mobilising power relations in panels when it comes to decision-making. Here, the role of the panel chair has proven to be relevant for gender-fair outcomes (Vinkenburg et al. 2021). Overall, decision-making methods used by review panels have been identified to impact the funding outcomes, giving specific relevance to ranking applications by specific criteria or procedures, called re-ranking.

Re-ranking policies and other instruments to mitigate gender bias might play a crucial role in panels (Bol et al. 2022), in particular in RFOs in which gender equality policies have been in place for some time. Feminist implementation studies (Carey et al. 2017) have raised awareness on complexities and potential pitfalls and barriers when implementing gender equality policies that are also relevant for analysing panel work in practice. With respect to gender awareness, we should also keep in mind that (research) organisations' organisational memory is limited (Van den Brink 2020).

2.2 Research questions

Against this background, we have identified the following research questions for studying practices of review panels in five selected European RFOs:

- (1) How are panels composed in general and by gender?
- (2) What is discussed in panels?
 - a. Which assessment/excellence criteria are applied?
 - b. In which way are they applied?
 - c. How is gender reflected in these discussions?
- (3) How is decision-making organised in panels?
 - a. What is the role of the panel chair?
 - b. How do panel members argue/discuss/negotiate when they have to agree on a common evaluation/score?
 - c. How are the decisions on the final scores of each application and the ranking of all applications organised? (And for some panels: how is the final decision-making on which applications to fund organised?)
- (4) How are formal gender equality policies implemented in practice?
 - a. In which ways do RFOs communicate the GE policies to the panels and encourage panels to implement these policies?
 - b. How do panel members (and remote reviewers) refer to and understand gender equality policies in relation to their work?

Further questions related to practices in peer review panels are addressed in different reports: Whether and how gender stereotypes are inscribed in language of reviews and applications will be answered in D6.2, based on linguistic data from the five case studies. Findings from a Randomised Control Trial (RCT),

analysing whether male and female applicants are assessed differently by reviewers, as well as the influence of the reviewer's gender on the assessment of proposals' PI by gender, are explored in part B of this deliverable.

2.3 Research on practices

To better understand what is going on in panels, we refer to the concept of 'practices' as "*activities which are situated, corporeal, and shaped by habitus without reflection*" (Poggio 2006). These social practices enable us to learn how gender is negotiated in panel practices by panel members' face-to-face interactions or in online panel meetings. When we understand gender as socially constructed through practices and negotiated in interactions, we follow Poggio's understanding of "*gender as situated social practice, or, in other words, something actualized through social interaction*" (Poggio 2006, 225). Gender and gender inequalities are therefore produced and reproduced through social practices and can be inscribed in social interactions, even if these interactions appear as gender-neutral to those involved. Therefore, it was relevant to understand how panel members made sense of their own actions and practices within panels, and thus their understanding of being a panel member.

In the GRANteD project, social practices have been studied by two methods producing different types of data: interviews with panellists at some time after the panel meetings, and participant observations of the panel meetings. In the participant observations, five panels in two different RFOs were observed. This allowed us to study how panel members interact, negotiate and discuss "*in real time and space*" (Martin 2006, 258). We were able to explore what panel members are "*literal(ly) saying or doing of gender*" (Martin, 2003) in real time when they discussed and negotiated their assessments of funding applications. Participatory observations enabled us to study general social practices and gender practices first-hand, for instance, when panel members were negotiating the applicants' scientific excellence, stating e.g., that this is a "*strong applicant, a well-known person in the field*". This 'practicing gender' is often done unpredictably and unintentionally, lacking awareness and intention and thus reflexivity (Martin 2006, 256). Thus, panel members might be practicing gender in panel meetings without being aware of it.

The main data source on practices are interviews with panel members including chairs from three different RFOs (and remote reviewers from another RFO). It would have been ideal, if the interviews were conducted immediately after the panel meetings, but for several logistic reasons this was not possible; this is why the interviews with panellists were conducted weeks after the panel meetings. In these interviews, the panellists reflected on their experiences from panel meetings, while also relating their individual perceptions of female and male researchers. The interviews made evident that panel members differ from each other regarding their awareness about how gender is inscribed into assessment practices or the science system on the whole (see for example 4.1.3).

Practices may show a general bias, for instance, when panel members apply criteria unfairly, in a way that their favoured applicant is supported and/or nepotism takes place. Practices can be gender-biased, for

⁴ As four out of five observations were held virtually, also the observation space was mostly a virtual one.

instance, when criteria are applied in a way favouring male candidates or female candidates, respectively. In case reviewers' practices differ explicitly or implicitly between men and women, favouring men over women or vice versa, we talk about **gendered practices** (Van den Brink & Benschop 2012). Gendered practices are a source for gender bias and may occur on different levels:

- (1) When general assessment policies which are seemingly gender-neutral are applied in panels, this might be done differently to female and male applicants (for instance, when mobility is checked for female applicants but not for male applicants). Criteria and indicators to assess excellence or merits can themselves be gendered, for instance, when criteria are applied which differently reflect the life context of female and male scientists, seeing masculine norms and values based on the stereotypical image of the ideal scientist as the norm (Nielsen 2017), for example, when considering the number of publications, with (the majority of) female researchers not having as much time to produce these publications.
- (2) Gendered practices might also occur when seemingly gender-neutral criteria are applied differently: Correll (2017) has pointed out practices where the assessment of female applicants is influenced by gendered role expectations and gendered stereotypes which lead to different funding outcomes compared to men, even in case women and men were equally qualified. The following practices were pointed out: performance and merit of women are inquired more thoroughly; the benchmarking bar for women is higher than for men; reviewers are weighting and shifting criteria to support their favoured applicant; and the existence of conflicting judgements of competence and likability for women but not for men.
- (3) When policies implemented to support gender fairness and to mitigate gender bias are applied in practice, this might lead to different outcomes for male and female applicants (for instance, when extension regulations are in place to compensate time loss for care work, this could be applied differently to male and female applicants).

The empirical work in GRANteD on practices primarily covers peer review panels, while practices of remote reviewers (who might also be called 'external reviewers') who were interviewed were only included in case they were of specific relevance for the assessment process.

2.4 Data collection

The GRANteD project established cooperation with five national RFOs in five European countries. For each RFO the GRANteD team **selected one specific funding programme** for more detailed data collection and analysis in close coordination with RFO representatives. The selected RFOs and respective specific funding programmes are the following:

- **FWF – Austrian Science Fund, Austria:** ESPRIT Career Advancement for Postdocs (<https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/fwf-programmes/esprit-programme>)
- **NCN – National Science Centre, Poland:** SONATA PhD holder grants (2–7 years after PhD degree) (<https://ncn.gov.pl/en/finansowanie-nauki/konkursy/typy/3>)
- **SFI – Science Foundation Ireland, Ireland: FFP (Projects) – Frontiers for the Future Programme** (<https://www.sfi.ie/funding/funding-calls/frontiers-for-the-future/index.xml>)

- **SRC – Swedish Research Council, Sweden:** IPD – International postdoc grant (<https://www.vr.se/english/applyingforfunding/calls/internationalpostdocgrant.5.2c821fd116dcb0e77cb2495.html>)
- **SRDA – Slovak Research and Development Agency, Slovakia:** GC – General Call (<https://www.apvv.sk/grantbr-schemes/general-call/vv-2020.html>)

The selection of the funding instruments and funding calls was done in bilateral communication within WP 2 and in Task 2.3 (Selecting RFOs for case studies). On the one hand, the selection reflected selection criteria defined in the GRANteD project and the time frame of the GRANteD project, and, on the other hand, the research interest on the part of RFOs. Some of the RFOs, for example, expressed interest in including, and having assessed, new funding instruments, or new elements within a funding process, which had recently been developed and implemented. Two such new funding approaches were included for two of the core-RFOs: FWF (Austria) and SFI (Ireland). Furthermore, the following dimensions were considered as particularly important for inclusion in the selection process: (i) different gender equality policies or elements of policies in place, (ii) different decision-making mechanisms and (iii) different instrument and grant types. It was also decided to primarily include instruments funding basic research (due to clearer career structures in academia and more developed indicators to measure performance/excellence in basic research).

The five RFOs agreed to provide access to data on the decision-making processes of the call under consideration in the GRANteD project (e.g. data on funding decisions, applicants, remote reviewers, panel members, panel composition), based on data needs specified in GRANteD Deliverable 2.1. Data specification and data exchange were defined in a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) that was signed by each RFO and GRANteD. Data collection was closely linked to the duration of the decision-making processes of the selected calls in 2020, 2021 and 2022.

Qualitative data were collected by semi-structured interviews with staff members, panel members and remote reviewers (if relevant) as well as by the observation of panels.

Combining observation and interview data provided in-depth information: While in interviews actors can be asked questions directly and can be quoted, we have no direct quotes from observations (besides short speaking notes). Observations do not allow for asking for direct information, for example, about how panel members perceive the atmosphere in the panel. In contrast, when observing panels, additional, more detailed data can be provided, for example, on behaviour and interaction between panel members and on how negotiating and decision-making is done in practice.

JOANNEUM RESEARCH was responsible for data collection and the analysis of FWF, SFI and SRDA; Örebro University for NCN and SRC.

The methods (qualitative interviews and observations) used for the collection of data for this report are outlined in the following section.

2.4.1 Interviews with staff, panel members and remote reviewers

Interviews were conducted with different actors of the assessment process of the respective calls (RFO management, RFO staff members, remote reviewers, panel chairpersons, vice panel chairpersons and panel members) (tasks WP 6.1. and 6.2). Originally, it was planned to conduct five interviews with staff members (management, equality advisers, members in other relevant positions) in each RFO and 20 interviews with panellists in each, including panel chairs and vice-chairs and/or remote reviewers.

Interview guidelines for each RFO for the staff member interviews and the panellists' interviews were developed together by the JOANNEUM RESEARCH and Örebro teams and included several different descriptive and evaluative research questions. Especially the guidelines for panellists' interviews served two functions: Firstly, the guideline aimed to generate data on the general meta-level across all RFOs. Therefore, some general questions were developed, which were used in all interviews with the panellists of all RFOs (e.g. How do gender equality and excellence relate to each other?). Secondly, the guidelines were adapted to the different conditions and contexts of the particular RFOs and the particular decision-making processes of the funding programmes in focus. This helped the interviewers to collect rich qualitative data which is specific to the RFOs and their funding programmes.

The RFOs provided lists with contact details of staff members, panel members and remote reviewers (if agreed on). Persons on these lists agreed on taking part in the GRANteD project by signing an Informed Consent sheet (IC). The GRANteD team selected interviewees following certain criteria defined in the GRANteD team: The GRANteD team aimed to interview panellists from different panels, but still selected those panels (if there were multiple panels, e.g. in case of NCN and SRDA) where the RFOs could collect most ICs. This would make it possible to interview several panellists from the same panel and thus receive different views on the same panel's work and the panel decision-making process. A gender-balanced selection of interviewees was also aimed for. Furthermore, in the case of the SFI, where the focus was more on interviewing the international remote reviewers rather than the panellists, a geographically balanced distribution for the selection of interviewees was considered as well. For NCN, which was the RFO with the largest number of panels (25), the selection criteria also included the consideration of an equal number of interviewees within each of the three major disciplinary fields, namely (i) Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, (ii) Physical Sciences and Engineering and (iii) Life Sciences.

However, approaching and reaching the different interviewees of the respective calls (staff, panel members, remote reviewers), especially when it came to panel members and remote reviewers (in the case of SFI), was somewhat challenging (even after they had signed the IC). In a first step, the GRANteD team reached out to the potential interviewees via email. If the recipients did not respond to these invitations, we tried again to contact them via email or even via phone (if phone numbers of the potential interviewees were available). If intended interviewees (especially panel members and remote reviewers) could not be reached or rejected the invitation, they were replaced with other panellists from the same panel. In only a few cases the GRANteD team got in touch with the contact person of the RFO and asked for support.

The qualitative data collection phase of the GRANteD project in WP 6 started in December 2020 and was completed in November 2022. In total the GRANteD team conducted 104 interviews (with staff members

and Scientific Council members, remote reviewers and panel members). 56 interviews were conducted with women and 48 with men.

A detailed overview of the number of interviews conducted per RFO is presented in Table 1 and Table 2. Table 1 shows the number of interviews conducted with staff members, Table 2 the number of interviews with panellists and remote reviewers. In total and across all RFOs, 33 interviews were conducted with staff members (20 with women, 13 with male staff members) and 71 with panellists and remote reviewers (36 with women and 35 with men). Most interviews were conducted online via video conferencing tools such as Zoom and equivalent tools. All interviews were conducted in English, in one case with the support of a translator. The interviews were recorded and transcribed.

Table 1: Interviews conducted with staff members

RFO	Number of Interviews conducted	Interviews conducted with female staff members	Interviews conducted with male staff members
FWF	7	5	2
NCN	5	3	2
SFI	5	5	0
SRC	7 ¹	3	4
SRDA	9 ²	4	5
Total number	33	20	13

Source: own table

¹ Interviews with SRC staff members included three interviews with Research Council members who are not formally staff members of SRC but have extensive knowledge on and insight into the research funding process.

² Interviews with SRDA staff members were conducted in oral and written format (four interviews were conducted in oral and five in written format).

Table 2: Interviews conducted with panel members (including chairpersons and vice-chairpersons) and remote reviewers

RFO – Funding programme	Number of panels (for interviews)	Number of Interviews conducted	Interviews conducted with women	Interviews conducted with men	Number of observed panels
FWF – ESPRIT 2021/2020	3	4	2	2	3
NCN – SONATA 17 ¹ 2021	11	27	13	14	0
SFI – FFP 2020	2	2 (panellists) 12 (remote reviewers)	2 (panellists) 7 (remote reviewers)	5 (remote reviewers)	2
SRC – IPD 2020	3	15	8	7	0
SRDA – General Call 2020	4	11	4	7	0
Total number	-	71	36	35	5

Source: own table

¹ NCN number their calls of the SONATA funding programme serially; in GRANteD we analysed the 17th call.

2.4.2 Observations of panel meetings

In addition to the qualitative interviews with staff, panel members and remote reviewers, observations were conducted in selected RFOs and panels. Observations enable a different type of data, generated in real time (as observational data is not impaired by the awareness and experiences of interviewed panel members, i.e. first-hand experiences can be collected). Therefore, observations provided complementary information and data on practices in panels.

When negotiating the MoU with the different RFOs, it became clear that observations were not possible in all settings. The SRC has conducted their own observation studies in their panels since 2012. NCN agreed on observations in the MoU, however, for this RFO qualitative interviews with panel members were chosen as the preferred method of data collection, firstly, as the interview method was expected to provide both broader and deeper knowledge on the understanding of panel members, which could not be observed during a panel meeting, and secondly, as the timing of the panel meetings collided with other tasks in GRANteD. Furthermore, there were no observations in SRDA panels due to language issues, as Slovak is the main language spoken during the panel meetings.

Observations of panel meetings were possible for the two SFI FFP 2020 panels and for three FWF Board meetings when ESPRIT applications were discussed. Due to the COVID-19 lockdown regulations at the time of observations, only the last FWF meeting could be held onsite, all other panels met and were observed online, which is why mainly remote participatory observation was used. Observation as a method for collecting data was already agreed on in the MoU that was signed in the initial phase of the GRANteD project. It states that panels can be observed in case that all panel members agree by Informed Consent (IC). IC from panel members was then directly collected by the RFOs.

Some applicants did not provide IC to participate in research, so when their applications were discussed, the GRANteD researchers were sent to breakout rooms or had to leave the room physically. This approach had previously been used for panel members in case of conflicts of interest and was thus well-established.

For collecting observation data, the GRANteD team developed an observation scheme, based on partners' experiences in observing panels in previous research projects. This observation scheme served as a checklist to keep the different dimensions to be observed in mind (such as the start and end time of each discussion, who speaks, who makes decisions, what is discussed, how often and in what form was a specific criterion mentioned). As data collection was virtual and also virtual panels were observed, the scheme had to be adapted (e.g. it was not possible to observe the seating arrangements of the panel). On the one hand, this adaptation benefitted from the ongoing analysis of interviews with SRC panel members who had already participated in virtual panel meetings due to COVID-19, as it allowed us to identify some relevant analytical dimensions. On the other hand, research on virtual teams and decision-making informed us about specific characteristics of virtual teams and virtual decision-making.

In each observation, two GRANteD researchers were present, who were briefly introduced by the panel chair before introducing themselves with short reference to the research project⁵. From then on, they were muted while the camera was on. It was agreed between the RFO and the observers that the GRANteD observers do not intervene in any form.

The two observers both took notes using the observation scheme. While one person was observing, the other person took notes on their previous observation. After each panel meeting, they reflected on their observations. In one RFO, audio-recording was allowed, but on one occasion there were technical problems, and on another it was not possible due to organisational issues in the meeting room.

Collecting data by participatory video-mediated observation was a new experience for the research team and it is of use to briefly sum up these experiences, as we became aware that at the time the observations were designed, only poor methodological guidance existed on how to do participant observations by video conferencing. Besides saving time and avoiding ecological footprint, it can be stated from a methodological perspective that in the GRANteD context, online participatory observation worked out well: Data protection was organised by IC, the panel members were already used to video conferencing and online meetings and even to doing review work remotely. So, for this target group, technical infrastructure and competence were no constraints for the quality of the observations, as already discussed in other projects: *"One of the most obvious challenges to data collection when conducting online fieldwork is that participants require stable and regular Internet access, in addition to technological competence and platform familiarity"* (Howlett 2021, 11). Further, it was also an advantage that video-mediated observations could be scheduled on short notice as in one case the last IC from a panel member arrived only on the day of the meeting.

We found that in video meetings, data are easy to collect: It is easier to listen and understand all panel members in the same quality compared to face-to-face panels. In online settings, it does not happen very often that two people speak at the same time, while in on-site panels, people sitting close to the researchers were sometimes chatting, while another panel member was talking, making it difficult to hear

⁵ When the panel members provided IC to the GRANteD research, they were already informed about the aims of this research project.

and understand the speaker. In the online format, all participants shared the same screen, so all had access to the same information. Sometimes panel members switched off the camera and it was not clear if they had also left the meeting briefly. In this case, context-specific information was missing that might have been available in on-site observations.

For GRANteD, no constraints were identified due to the virtual observation mode. Experiences based on the virtual panel format are discussed in chapter 4.2.4.

2.5 Data analysis

The research strategy adopted in WP 6 is of qualitative character. The empirical data analysed comprised recorded and transcribed interviews with staff members and panellists and/or remote reviewers as well as the observation schemes and notes taken during the observations of the FWF and SFI panel meetings (as explained in 2.4). The data preparation and data analysis for each RFO took place in different periods between 2020 and 2022, always shortly after the data collection was completed. The task of collecting and analysing qualitative data was shared between the two partners involved: While JOANNEUM RESEARCH was responsible for the collection and analysis of data from FWF, SFI and SRDA, Örebro University worked on NCN and SRC data (as already mentioned above).

A common methodology was developed and experiences were reflected on by the partners in regular online meetings. Two persons of each RFO worked together on one RFO, collecting data and cross-checking coding in the data analysis.

2.5.1 Developing a coding tree for analysis

The approach used for the systematic data preparation, coding and analysis of the collected information from the interviews and observations is based on the qualitative content analysis developed by Mayring. Mayring defines qualitative content analysis as *“an approach of empirical, methodological controlled analysis of texts within their context of communication, following content analytic rules and step by step models, without rash quantification”* (Mayring, 2000, 2). The approach is explained by Patton (2002, 453) as *“any qualitative data reduction and sense-making effort that takes a volume of qualitative material and attempts to identify core consistencies and meanings”*. Therefore, qualitative content analysis condenses raw data into categories or themes based on valid inference and interpretation. This process can use inductive or deductive approaches to develop categories or themes from the raw material. For the deliverable D 6.1, a mixed approach with deductive and inductive elements was chosen.

The first RFO, for which the data collection and data preparation (transcribing the recorded staff and panellists' interviews) was completed, was SRC in spring 2020. The SRC data built the testing ground for the development of the coding tree for the analysis. This coding tree then was used for the coding and analysis of all other RFOs in focus.

In the course of a thematic analysis, patterns were identified in the SRC data and first categories/themes were developed. These themes later on entered the coding tree as meta-level codes. Following Braun and Clarke (2006, 82) *“a theme captures something important about the data in relation to the research question, and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set”*. Themes can be

broad and expansive or more focused and specific and they can come from both data (inductive approach) and our theoretical understanding (a priori approach).

For the thematic analysis of the SRC data, a mixed inductive-deductive approach was used and initial themes were discovered in the interviews by looking for repetitions, similarities/differences, theory-related issues, key words, but also missing data. The development of themes was the outcome of multiple steps. First, the GRANteD partners who coded the data of the SRC case familiarised themselves with the interview transcripts, read and re-read them and generated initial codes by coding interesting features across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code. Then, in a second step, these generated codes were collated into potential themes and it was checked again in relation to the data whether these themes “work out”. To refine the themes, they were properly termed and defined to “...*identify the ‘essence’ of what each theme is about*” (Braun & Clarke 2006, 92). A total of six main themes were identified, each consisting of several subthemes. The six main themes that emerged from this preliminary data coding of SRC were the following:

- Gender dynamics in the panel work
- Evaluation in practice
- Understanding of gender in science/academia/society
- GE policies
- Improving the funding process in general
- Impact of COVID-19

The six main themes served as a deductive analytical framework for the analysis of the data collected from the following four RFOs (FWF, NCN, SFI, SRDA). For the data coding and data analysis of these RFOs, a deductive coding tree was developed based on the initial themes. The themes outlined above entered this coding tree as meta-level codes. Additional meta-level codes and sub-codes for these meta-level codes were derived from the interview guideline.

2.5.2 Using the coding tree for analysis

During the coding process, new codes inductively emerged from the data. The new codes were mainly specific sub-level codes (or subthemes) for the already existing meta-level codes in the coding tree, covering a specific facet of these meta-level codes. Sometimes interviews also provided data which entered new meta-level codes. It has to be mentioned that a considerable part of the codes that were developed inductively were specific to a certain RFO and its funding instrument in focus, i.e. they were not necessarily relevant for all other RFOs. Furthermore, for the two RFOs with observation data (FWF and SFI), further detailed codes were added for specific meta-level codes, for instance, for language use when discussing scientific excellence. In chapter 7.1 of the annex, the general coding tree (without the RFOs’ specific meta- and sub-level codes) is presented.

The coding process allowed us to assign a unit of text to more than one category simultaneously. Still, when developing the coding tree, the GRANteD team followed the principle of Lincoln and Guba (1985), which states that codes in a coding scheme should be defined in a way that they are internally as homogeneous as possible and externally as heterogeneous as possible. Furthermore, for the internal use in the project

team and among the persons who coded the interviews and observation sheets and analysed them, a coding manual, which consisted of category names, definitions and rules for assigning codes as well as coding examples, was developed. To test the clarity and consistency of the meta-level and sub-level codes of the coding tree, a sample of interviews was coded. Then, at least another person coded this sample of interviews as well to find out if meta- and sub-level codes are understood in the same way (multiple-eyes principle). After this testing process, the coding was compared and the coding tree and its manual were revised where needed. Additionally, there were regular meetings with all GRANteD project partners who were involved in conducting the interviews and the interview analysis in WP 6 to discuss the progress of the coding, any difficulties that emerged and how to deal with them.

This coding tree formed the general framework for the data analysis. The analysis process – as well as the coding process – was carried out for each RFO separately. The analysis process was aimed to make sense of the codes and themes developed before and during the coding process. The process was characterised by exploring properties and dimensions of the meta- and sub-level codes, identifying relationships between the codes, uncovering patterns and testing codes against the full range of data (Bradley, 1993). The analysis focused on meta-level and/or sub-level codes which captured information on specificities of the funding programmes in focus, decision-making processes and overall challenges in these decision-making processes.

2.5.3 Case study reports

The outcomes of the analysis process were prepared in separate case study reports for each RFO. The findings from the five case studies of the RFOs' funding programmes were presented to each RFO for feedback and discussion.

These case study reports build the basis for the synthesis of findings in this deliverable. The structure of the reports was developed in a relatively uniform way to support a qualitative synthesis analysis. However, each case report addressed the specific peculiarities of the funding instruments in focus.

To make the outcomes of this analysis useable for the GRANteD multivariate model that analyses gender bias in WP 4 and WP 9, some variables were identified and data provided for each of the five case studies. This covers the analysis of panel practices in WP 6, data from the policy analysis in WP 5 and administrative data provided by the RFOs (see annex, 7.2).

2.6 Data use

Qualitative data used in this report is anonymised so that individual informants are impossible to identify. When working with the data, a two-step-approach was used for its anonymisation: When developing the text of this report, we worked with codings clearly identifying the interviewees, their RFO, panel and function, as well as the observations, so that it was clear which data source they belong to.

For data protection reasons, we simplified these codes in this document, to preserve anonymity and increase research integrity. This is in particular relevant as some RFOs have a small number of panels making it easy to identify the informant. After each direct quote a code indicates to which RFO this quote refers and if this quote was taken from an interview with staff, a panel chair or members, remote reviewers or

observers of panel meetings. If the quote refers to something that was said during GRANteD observations, this is indicated by using the code for the RFO, the function of the person, who said it, and the term 'observation'. The following table indicates the codes for the respective RFO.

Table 3: Codes of the respective RFO used for quotes in the document

RFO	Code of RFO
FWF	B
NCN	D
SFI	C
SRC	A
SRDA	E

Source: own table

3 CONTEXT FOR PRACTICES IN PANELS

3.1 Gender equality policies in place

The risk of gender bias in the GRANteD core-RFOs was assessed to range from considerable and substantial to relatively low. The findings of D5.1 showed that especially the RFOs which do not address gender equality at organisational level, are silent about gender and gender equality in their actions, measures and procedures and do not collect or do not publish gender-disaggregated data have a higher risk of gender bias in their decision-making process (Husu and Peterson 2022).

FWF and SRC are RFOs with a long tradition of gender action and comprehensive gender equality policies in place. These RFOs have been working for more than 20 years addressing gender challenges in research funding and striving to establish an equal and fair funding system and processes. SFI has more recently started to engage actively in gender equality promotion, but have developed and broadened its policies in a quick pace. These three RFOs demonstrate awareness of most of the factors in the seven potential gender bias risk areas identified in the policy analysis in D 5.1.⁶, and are continuously taking action to counteract the factors which may lead to or open up potential gender bias in processes of the RFOs. Measures, actions and procedures which can be considered good standard regarding gender equality are anchored in their organisation, structures and processes (e.g. GE strategies and/or GE action plans, RFOs aim for gender-balanced decision-making bodies and gender-balanced panels and reviewers, monitoring of gender-disaggregated data, guidelines and/or training on assessment procedures and the evaluation criteria for panellists and reviewers also addressing GE and unconscious bias).

Moreover, these RFOs aim to adopt findings found at international or European level to fine-tune their funding programmes or even to test new measures with regard to gender equality. FWF, for example, has

⁶ The seven potential gender bias risk areas identified in the policy analysis in D5.1. are 1) Strategy, 2) Structure, 3) Communication and Language, 4) Criteria (evaluation and eligibility), 5) Transparency, 6) Accountability, 7) Monitoring.

given up two women-only funding programmes recently and instead established the new funding programme ESPRIT for early career researchers in 2021. The ESPRIT programme guarantees a gender-balanced outcome, so that 50 % of ESPRIT grants should be allocated to female and 50 % to male applicants ('quota' measure). The quota measure can be understood in a broader sense as a re-ranking measure. Re-ranking measures are also implemented in the Frontiers for the Future Programme (FFP) of SFI and the International Postdoc Programme (IPD) of SRC. In the case of FFP, applications from female candidates are given priority in the event of applications receiving the same final score; in the case of SRC, when ranking applications that have been rated to be of equal scientific quality, applicants from the underrepresented gender can be prioritised. Furthermore, female applicants are especially encouraged to apply in all three funding programmes. FWF organises special ESPRIT workshops for female applicants in the run-up to the application, and SFI places particular emphasis on the promotion of women and 'emerging investigators'⁷ in general. SFI and FWF also ask their applicants to discuss the sex and gender dimension in research and innovation (GIRI) in their research proposals and SFI has implemented the narrative CV following the DORA declaration only recently. Additionally, in all three programmes (ESPRIT, FFP, IPD), other measures to mitigate gender imbalances in funding decision outcomes are in place, which are not specific for these calls, but also hold for all other calls of the RFOs (e.g., considering career breaks and academic age, guidelines and/or training for decision-making bodies, panels and reviewers regarding gender equality and unconscious bias).

NCN and SRDA are – compared to FWF, SFI and SRC – emerging RFOs in respect to gender equality and diversity measures. Both RFOs have only recently started to engage with GE topics, which is why at the time of data collection in the GRANteD project, there were only few structures, strategies, guidelines and/or trainings in place with regard to GE. The only explicitly gender equality related measure in place within SRDA and the NCN at the time of the data collection in GRANteD was that reviewers and/or panellists need to consider maternity/paternity or parental leave while evaluating quality, skills and competence of the responsible researcher and team members (with NCN only referring to career breaks for mothers). SRDA also takes the age and length of the professional career of the responsible researcher and team members into account, while NCN additionally commits itself to the existence of a non-biased review process, which is also illustrated by NCN signing the DORA convention. These measures hold for all funding programmes within NCN and SRDA, including the two programmes in focus in the GRANteD project. However, it has to be mentioned that near the end of the GRANteD project (in 2022), NCN developed and decided on their first Gender Equality Plan (GEP).

In general, it was stated by a representative from an RFO management that RFOs do play a role in respect to gender equality in science and also in review panels and that *"one of the key roles of funding organisations is to create a culture, a culture in the whole science landscape where diversity and gender equality are taken for granted"* (B, panel member). It was, however, stressed that this is not only their responsibility, but that *"gender equality can be solved solely in the interaction between funding*

⁷ Emerging investigators are defined as researchers who did not previously hold a significant SFI research award or who are re-entering the competitive scientific field after a period of eligible leave from research. The review scores of applicants who are categorised as 'emerging investigators' will be weighted so that there is more emphasis on the quality of the research than on the track record.

organisation, research institutions and policies (...) The funding organisations can set standards, this is one of their key roles” (B, panel member).

3.2 Panel composition

Panels widely differ regarding their composition and function across RFOs. The following sections discuss the different panel compositions and their specific characteristics. Table 4 summarises the main findings.

Table 4: Panel composition of each RFO and funding programme

RFO, funding programme & call	Total number of panels	International/national panels	Total number of panellists (incl. chairs), % of women & men panellists	Aim for certain % of women panellists
FWF: ESPRIT 2021/2022	3	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number: 110 Women: 38,2 % (42) Men: 61,8 % (68) 	aim for gender balance
NCN: SONATA 17 2021	25	Mainly international	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number: 385 Women: 27,5 % (106) Men: 72,5 % (279) 	aim for gender balance when possible
SFI: FFP 2020	2	International	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number: 26 Women: 38,5 % (10) Men: 61,5 % (16) 	aim for 40 %
SRC: IPD 2020	3	Mainly national	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number: 41 Women: 48,8 % (20) Men: 51,2 % (21) 	at least 40 % of underrepresented gender
SRDA: GC 2020	6	National (with one expert from outside Slovakia per panel)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total number: 97 Women: 17,5 % (17) Men: 82,5 % (80) 	no

Source: own table

3.2.1 Number, size and thematic fields of panels

The number of panels established in the different funding programmes in focus range from two panels in the FFP instrument of the SFI to 25 panels in the SONATA instrument of the NCN⁸. Furthermore, the size of the panels varies between the different funding programmes in focus and within the funding programmes themselves. Most of the panels across all funding programmes have at least ten panel members (including chairpersons and vice-chairpersons, if the position of vice chairperson exists, in 34 out of 39 panels); there are very few panels with more than 20 panel members (six out of 39 panels) or with fewer than ten panel members (two out of 39). Greater variations in the size of panels within the funding programmes themselves can be observed in the SONATA (NCN) and the GC (SRDA) funding programmes. The size of panels of the NCN SONATA funding programme varies between nine and 20 panel members (including chairpersons); the one of the SRDA GC funding programme between nine and 26 panel members (including

⁸ From 2022, NCN has used 26 panels instead of 25. One more ST panel (Physical Sciences and Engineering) was added.

chairpersons and vice-chairpersons). Those are also the funding programmes with the highest number of panels established (SONATA: 25 panels; GC: six panels). In the other funding programmes, there are only two active panels (FFP funding programme) or three panels (ESPRIT⁹ and IDP funding programme) with a fairly similar size. It should be noted that the panels used for assessing the applications for the ESPRIT and SONATA instruments also assess proposals submitted for other calls. The SRC IDP and the SFI FFP panels *only* assess applications for this call.

Following the OECD classification of fields of science and technology (FOS2002)¹⁰, it becomes clear that all funding programmes but one cover the whole range of FOS with their panels. The FFP funding programme of SFI is the only funding programme analysed that does not cover Social Sciences and Humanities, but the other four FOS with two panels. One panel focuses on Life Sciences and Health, and another panel on Chemistry, Physical Sciences, etc. In the case of the GC funding programme of SRDA, the panels are even thematically aligned to the six FOS and named accordingly. Panels of the SONATA funding programme of NCN and the IPD funding programme of SRC are grouped by FOS. The IPD funding programme has one panel for Humanities and Social Sciences, Educational Sciences and Artistic Research; one for Medicine and Health Sciences and one for Natural and Engineering Sciences. In the SONATA funding programme, six panels cover various disciplines of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences; ten panels cover disciplines of Physical Sciences and Engineering and nine panels cover disciplines of Life Sciences. The panels discussing the FWF ESPRIT funding programme cover all six FOS. Three meetings of the FWF Board took place in the time of data collection in the GRANteD project. One thing that holds for FWF is that the member composition of the FWF panels is supposed to be stable, participants vary slightly from meeting to meeting when members could not attend and were replaced by representatives. Therefore, each FWF meeting is regarded as a separate panel for the purpose of analysis.

3.2.2 Selection process and gender balance

The existence and transparency of formal regulations regarding the selection process of panel members varies among the five RFOs analysed by GRANteD. The panel composition of FWF, SFI and SRC is highly regulated, including principles of gender balance. There are guidelines on the composition of panels for each funding call, concerning the number of panellists, the maximum time of service as a member and chair as well as the expertise required. In the case of the SRC, the Director General appoints the chairs and members of the panels, following the proposals by the Scientific Councils' Secretaries General; in the case of FWF, panel members are delegated from various Austrian research organisations based on a legal basis. SFI oversight sitting panel members are distinguished international peer reviewers selected on the basis of the respective subject.

There are guidelines on the composition of SRDA and NCN panels as well. These guidelines concern the number of panellists, the maximum time of service as a member and chair. However, they lack transparency and formal regulations regarding selection criteria and the overall selection process. In the case of SRDA, relevant Slovakian authorities and stakeholders (e.g. Slovak Academy of Sciences, Council of Higher

⁹ Three out of five panels per year were observed.

¹⁰ The OECD classified the fields of science and technology in six distinguished fields: 1) Natural Sciences; 2) Engineering and Technology; 3) Medical and Health Sciences; 4) Agricultural Sciences; 5) Social Sciences; 6) Humanities.

Education Institutions, associations of different market sectors, companies with more than 500 employees) send nominations of possible candidates to the SRDA panels. The SRDA Presidium then selects and nominates panel members from these candidates. However, there are no formalised rules for the selection of panel members (e.g. regarding expertise required) yet, which might lead to arbitrariness or informal invitations. In contrast, interviews with staff members and panel members of the NCN revealed how competences and the expertise of panel members might be assessed. The NCN Scientific Council identifies researchers and academics who can become expert reviewers (i.e. panel members and panel chairs). They are selected among what is described as “*outstanding Polish and foreign researchers, holding at least a PhD degree*” (source: information about the SONATA 17 call).

The interviews with staff members of all RFOs but SRDA indicated that a clear goal of their institutions is to have gender-balanced panels. FWF, SFI and SRC even state this goal formally in their GEPs or other relevant policy documents. SRC particularly stands out in this regard: According to the SRC GEP, equal gender distribution should be strived for (at least 40 % of the underrepresented gender), and there is a monitoring mechanism in place. If equal gender distribution is not achieved, reasons for this need to be justified to the Director General, including a list of invited reviewers of the underrepresented gender who have declined (see, for example, SRC Guidelines for the composition of the IPD panel, fall 2020).

As Table 4 indicates, men are the majority among SRC panellists, but the institutionalised efforts of RFOs regarding gender balance of their panels are reflected in the numbers of women and men panel members. 48,8 % of all SRC panellists of the IDP call 2020 were women, 51,2 % were men. All three SRC panels were close to or were gender-balanced. Two of the three IPD Panel Chairs were women in this call round. Overall, the FWF panels discussing ESPRIT applications were near to gender balance: In two panels, 39 % of the members were women, in one meeting 37 %. Overall, the SFI panels for the FFP call 2020 showed a similar gender balance as those of FWF. In total, 38,5 % of all panellists were women, 61,5 % were men. However, when looking at the panel composition by sex of each panel, it is obvious that while 57 % of the members in the panel concerning Life and Health Sciences were women, including the chair (eight out of 14), the second panel (covering Chemistry, Physical Sciences, ICT, for example) had only two women, while ten members were men (including the chair). So only 17 % were female panel members. In this regard, SFI staff informants reported that they had worked hard to find more female panel members, but had not been successful in increasing their number.

The panel composition by sex of the NCN SONATA call 2022 and the SRDA GC call 2020 is far from being gender-balanced. Of the 385 panel members (including chairs) assessing the SONATA 17 applications in 2022, 279 were men (72,5 %) and 106 (27,5 %) were women. This means that of the 25 panels only eight were gender-balanced in 2022 (with women and men constituting between 40–60% of the total panel members). One panel (consisting of twelve panel members) had only male panel members and five panels (consisting of between eleven to 20 panel members) had only one woman panel member – in all six cases the woman had the role of panel chair. These very biased panels were all within the field of Physical Sciences and Engineering. Of the 25 panel chairs 14 were male and eleven were female. However, during the kick-off meeting with GRANteD in 2021, NCN stated that one of their aims was “*when possible, trying to reach a gender balance in the expert teams*” (i.e. the review panels). In the new GEP (from 2022), NCN also includes “*improving gender balance in expert teams*” as one of the goals.

Of the 97 panellists assessing the GC call 2020, 17,5 % were women, 82,5 % were men. All SRDA panels had a clear minority of female panellists, none exceeding the 30 % mark (Medical Sciences Council). In half of the panels only around one out of ten panellists were women (Natural Sciences Council, Technical Sciences Council and Humanities Council)¹¹. Women are even more underrepresented when it comes to the Council Chair and Vice-Chair position, even though in almost each scientific field in Slovakia, the proportion of women researchers has moved close to gender parity or even above it (see She-Figures 2021). There were only one female chairperson and one female vice-chairperson. The female chairperson was in the Humanities Council, where she was the only woman; the female vice-chairperson was in the Social Sciences Council. At the time of data collection in the GRANteD project, the establishment of gender-balanced panels as a future priority was not (yet) mentioned as a formal goal.

3.2.3 *Conflict of interest and internationality of panels*

Some RFOs have established (mainly) national panels (FWF, SRC and SRDA) for the funding instruments in focus, others work with international panels (NCN and SFI). International panels have the advantage that panel members have less often a conflict of interest (CoI) with applicants. In SFI panels, CoI is checked long before the panel meeting, and in both SFI panels observed, no CoI emerged. In contrast, in FWF panels, where all members work in Austrian research institutions, CoI is more common, and in each meeting observed several panel members were sent to breakout rooms (online panels) or had to leave the meeting room physically (on-site panel).

If panels are composed of national panellists only, it is even more important that strict CoI policies are formalised, implemented and monitored. A best practice example in this regard is the SRC. The SRC Board adopted a detailed CoI Policy and guidelines on how to manage CoI in 2019. The policy and guidelines are included in the reviewer handbooks and are available on the SRC website. The CoI policy is based on the Administrative Procedure Act (Förvaltningslagen, SFS 2017:900). The interviews confirmed a high attention to implementing the CoI policy in different phases of the panel work, from the allocation of the reviewer tasks to discussion and decision-making. One SRC panel discusses the CoI in the specific case of a postdoc grant, like the IPD of SRC:

“Well, there are clear guidelines from the Research Council, you should not have collaborated with the person, you should not have family ties or you shouldn’t be friends. Some people are taking this very extremely tight and if I am an evaluator of a presumptive postdoc and I know the supervisor, who was a PhD supervisor, you know, I’m not a friend but I just happened to kind of know this person, then they say I have a conflict of interest[...].” (A, panel chair)

Another panel chair added that it would be an embarrassment to panel members if they would violate CoI and it would come to light: *“No, but you know, people know people, so if they see that there is a panel member who discusses an application and they know that this person knows that person that would be very bad, so people are very careful.”* (A, panel chair)

NCN changed from having panels constituted by exclusively Polish researchers to international panels a few years ago. The main reason for this decision was to decrease corruption, COI and bias. Most of the

¹¹ Note that panels at SRDA are called “Councils”.

international panel members and chairs are from other European countries. There are also some Polish researchers who are active in other countries. Besides reducing problems of COI in an international panel, other benefits for the competitiveness of Polish science were also emphasised regarding receiving international feedback. Despite the majority of panel members being from abroad, there are still strict policies and regulations regarding COI in NCN. A reviewer cannot review and cannot participate in the meeting when the panel discusses an application from a PI who is active at the same university.

The risk of nepotism and corruption was also identified as considerable risk in the analysis of SRDA. Decision-making bodies (remote reviewers and panellists) of the GC 2020 primarily consisted of Slovakian and Czech researchers. Due to the small country size of Slovakia, where researchers from a scientific field know each other, COI seems to be challenging. Here, it has to be mentioned that the interviews confirmed that the SRDA is aware of this risk and is currently in the process of changing the decision-making process and establishing international panels as well.

However, reaching out to the international community to establish international panels poses a major problem to many RFOs. It is harder to attract panellists from abroad than national scholars. Reasons vary from foreign scholars not being familiar with the science and funding system to being occupied with other work and duties or the time it takes to travel to panel meetings, etc. So, to keep time investment for panel meetings limited, the FFP funding programme of SFI will continue to be held solely online. Panel members do not have to travel to Ireland for the panel meetings. That saves time and panel meetings can more easily be integrated into the time schedules of panellists.

3.3 Panel function

In this section, practices preceding panel meetings, the role of the panel and the panel chair as well as the presence and role of other panel members, including observers, are discussed.

Table 5: Characteristics and specifics of the funding programmes in focus

RFO, funding programme & call	Stages of decision-making	Panel function	Specifics in the decision-making process
FWF: ESPRIT 2021/2022	Two-stage process with the involvement of remote reviewers in the first stage	Confirming or adjusting Office suggestion, deciding on funding	RFO staff is present, but does not intervene
NCN: SONATA 2021	Two-stage process with the involvement of remote reviewers in the second stage	Reviewing and ranking the applications, deciding which to send to remote reviewers, agreeing on which to be suggested to the council to be funded	RFO staff is present to inform about rules and regulations and keep the protocol but does not intervene in the assessment
SFI: Frontiers for the Future Programme 2020 (FFP 2020)	Two-stage process with the involvement of remote reviewers in the first stage	Discussing and assessing the quality and fairness of remote reviews	Rebuttal: Applicants' possibility to respond to remote reviewers' assessment

			New panel function: Reviewing and assessing fairness of remote reviews
SRC: International Postdoc 2020 (IPD 2020)	One-stage review panel process	Reviewing and ranking the applications	Gender as a borderline condition in case applications have equal scientific quality Observers present in the meetings, reporting to the Research Councils
SRDA: General Call 2020 (GC 2020)	Two-stage process with the involvement of remote reviewers in the first stage	Presenting a draft version of consensus on the basis of the remote reviews, ranking applications, providing draft decision	Computer-based selection process of remote reviewers based on a match of the scientific discipline of the reviewer and the scientific discipline stated in the proposal of the applicant

Source: own table

3.3.1 Practices preceding panel meetings

The funding programmes analysed by GRANteD follow multiple stages for decision-making. All RFOs except SRC involve a two-stage process as the decision-making process. For the specific funding scheme analysed here (IPD), SRC has a one-stage process for reviewing and ranking, but the final funding decisions are not made in the panels but by the SRC General Director. After an eligibility check performed by RFO staff, the applications are distributed to remote reviewers in three of the funding programmes (FWF, SFI, SRDA). The first stage of FWF, SFI and SRDA involves a peer review by remote reviewers. The number of remote reviewers that are asked to review the same application depends on the RFO. In case of the SFI, three remote reviewers peer-review the same application, in case of FWF and SRDA there are (at least) two remote reviewers.

NCN does not involve a peer review by remote reviewers in the first stage. Instead, each panel member receives approximately ten to 15 proposals to evaluate for the individual review and each proposal is evaluated by two panel members. This individual reviewing process, which involves only a short version of the proposal, leads to the first panel meeting where all proposals are discussed. One of the two panel members who review the application is appointed to be the rapporteur, a role that involves tasks such as presenting the application during the meeting and writing up the final assessment. The outcome of the first panel meeting is a recommendation of which proposals to retain for the second stage, in which the full versions of selected proposals are sent to external experts.

At FWF, SFI and SRDA, in the second stage, applications reviewed by remote reviewers on the basis of assessment criteria of the respective RFOs proceed to a final panel and proposals deemed to be fundable by the panel are ranked based on their final score. In all three RFOs, the panels can adjust the score given by the remote reviewers, following certain criteria and rules. Moreover, SFI has an additional element in the process: It asks all applicants to respond to reviewers' comments. After receiving the response (rebuttal), the remote reviewers can or may adjust their scores. Then, two SFI panel members check the

quality and fairness of the remote reviews remotely, and only when the two do not agree, the application is discussed in the panel. At FWF, all applications are discussed in the panel except the ones where the FWF office agreed on a grade C after having checked the assessment of the remote reviewers. These applications are rejected immediately and are not passed on to the panel meetings for discussion. Only proposals which have received a score over a certain score in the assessment from the remote reviewers will end up in the final panel phase of FWF, SFI and SRDA.

In the second stage of the NCN decision-making process, the full applications are reviewed by at least two and up to five remote reviewers. These remote reviewers are often foreign experts. The reviews from the remote reviewers are later discussed by the expert team/panels during a second panel session. This second panel meeting is often shorter than the first meeting as there are fewer proposals to discuss.

The decision-making process of the SRC IPD funding programme is characterised – in contrast to the other RFOs – as a one-stage review panel process, meaning that first, at least three members of the respective SRC panel, in some cases even more, review and score the proposals. One of the reviewers, the rapporteur, shortly introduces the proposal to the panel. The reviewers (mainly Swedish researchers), who are panel members at the same time discuss and adjust the scores, rank the applications and make a proposal for a decision to the Director General. A certain proportion of the applications with the lowest grades based on the three individual reviews are screened out (sifted) before or at the beginning of the review panel meeting. These applications will not be discussed in detail by the panel, giving room to a more detailed discussion of the more highly ranked applications by the reviewers. However, any panellist can request to bring an application up from the sifted list for panel discussion.

Figure 1: Funding processes of the respective RFO in focus

Source: own figure

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

3.3.2 *Various panel functions*

The functions of panels differ between the five RFOs in the focus of GRANteD. Depending on the respective RFO, panels perform different tasks. Therefore, the panels of some funding instruments have a greater decision-making power in the decision-making process than those of other funding instruments. For example, panels of the NCN SONATA funding programme have multiple functions and meet twice: During the first meeting, the panels sift the applications that have passed eligibility checks and select which should be sent to remote reviewers, who are experts on the specific topic of the application. Based on these reviews, they develop a shortlist of applications sent to the remote review. During the second meeting, the panels discuss the final ranking of the applications, based on their own assessment and the assessment and comments from the external expert. They agree on which applications to be suggested to the NCN to be funded. Funding decisions are always made by the NCN council, based on recommendations of panels, and the council rarely deviates from the panels' suggestions.

In all other funding instruments in focus, panels meet only once. In the case of FWF and SFI, the panels take up a kind of control function. Panels of the ESPRIT funding programme confirm or adjust the suggestion of which applications to be funded made by the FWF office¹² and finally decide on funding. During the panel meeting, the panel member responsible presents the application, the scores provided by the two remote reviewers and the preliminary final grade suggested by the FWF office to the panel, taking into account comments of the alternate¹³. The panel member responsible for a specific application highlights its strengths and weaknesses and discusses the comments of the two international remote reviewers and the FWF office.

In the case of SFI, panels have recently taken over the role of control body of the remote reviewer process. They discuss and assess the quality and fairness of remote reviews. This way, SFI has widely shifted the decision-making power from the panel members to the remote reviewers. Panel members have access to all information regarding the application, but do not decide on it. Some panel members raised the question in the feedback round after the panel meeting¹⁴, if the panel is needed at all and whether the full quality assurance of remote reviews could be done automatically (e.g. by use of standard deviation scores of the different reviewers). It was also discussed whether it would be more beneficial that the three remote reviewers meet in a 'mini panel' to exchange their views.

Formally, the panels of SRC and SRDA have a similar function. In both cases, panel members are rapporteurs and present the reviews of a certain application to the panel. However, in case of SRC, the panel members are, at the same time, the reviewers of the applications (review panel); panel members of SRDA do not have this double function. For each application, two panel members of SRDA develop a joint draft of consensus based on the two independent reviews of the remote reviewers. SRDA panels discuss the reviews of the remote reviewers, but also the applications themselves (mainly in case of ambiguities). Ambiguities in the

¹² The FWF office consists of the scientific project officers and the reporters assigned to the different applications.

¹³ Each panel member of the FWF panels have one alternate, who is also responsible for the same applications and, in case of an absence of the respective panel member at the panel meeting, represents this person at the meeting.

¹⁴ The feedback round after the formal panel meeting of the panel members regarding the new function of SFI panels was also part of the observation by the GRANteD team.

assessments of remote reviewers take more time for discussion and may lead to a change of the average score (see also 4.3.1). The panel provides a draft decision on each application to the SRDA.

Similarly, in the case of SRC, the entire review panel discusses and ranks the applications, starting with each application reviewed by three panel members being shortly introduced by the rapporteur, followed by a discussion by the other reviewers and other panellists, after which the panel concludes a draft rating. At the penultimate stage, when all applications are rated, the panel can consider re-ranking of applications of the underrepresented gender for applications which have been assessed to be of equal scientific quality. Finally, the panel makes a proposal for a decision to the Director General.

3.3.3 Role of panel chair

Panel meetings follow predetermined rules set by the respective RFO. In most RFOs, the chair plays an important role in adhering to these rules (FWF, SFI, SRC and SRDA). A major responsibility of chairpersons and, if existing, vice-chairpersons, besides preparing and moderating the panel meetings, is to keep order, to monitor time and ensure rules being observed during the panel meetings, prevent that discussions go in the wrong direction or lead to an argument and make sure that there is an appropriate language culture during the meetings. In this regard, panel chairs are also supported by staff of the respective RFOs who attend panel meetings. In this respect, the role of panel chairs can be understood as facilitators. In the case of NCN, the coordinators (NCN staff/scientific officers) who also attend the panel meetings know all the rules and keep order, etc. In this respect, the NCN chairs have a rather passive role regarding NCN rules and practical details. The description of the role of the chair, however, varied between members of different panels. They were also described as having a key role in managing the discussions when the panel needed to reach an agreement on assessments and scoring.

Furthermore, panel chairs are probably the only persons in the whole panel who skim through all projects or at least read all abstracts. This is especially important for the chairs that assign each application to the panel members (as, for example, in NCN and SRC). In the interviews with SRC chairs, panellists and observers, it was also often highlighted that chairs have to take the requirement of gender balance into account, and that decisions are reached in a fair and consensual manner. In FWF panels, it was observed how the chair – who chairs all panel meetings – steered the process for achieving a gender-balanced outcome at the end of the panel meeting and on some occasions put an end to gender-related discussions that did not lead anywhere. In SFI, no gender-related activities of the chairs were observed.

Despite the predetermined rules set by the respective RFOs, the interviews showed that each chairperson has their own expectations, rules and style concerning how to manage meetings. There are chairpersons who give more space for discussion to the panel members and who do not intervene very often, only in cases where rules are obviously not respected, whereas other chairpersons wanted to exercise more control over the discussions taking place in the panel meetings.

3.3.4 Presence and role of other panel members, including observers

In all RFOs, staff members (e.g. administrative staff members, programme officers/coordinators) also attend panel meetings. They have a formal function, provide detailed formal information if requested or assist chairpersons regarding organisational or technical issues, for example, in case of the online panel

meetings (mainly during the COVID-19 pandemic). During the panel meetings (online and face to face), the role of these staff members may also include displaying the list of the applications during the meeting and keeping track of which application is currently assessed and showing the correct application, sometimes strongly supported by IT infrastructure (SFI). In case of NCN, the staff members present at panel meetings, called coordinators (= scientific officers responsible for the organisation of calls) also have the information about how many applications can be funded and can thus assist in the decision on how many applications to send to the second stage and on to the remote review. Furthermore, they also evaluate the impartiality of the review process.

Also, in SRC and FWF panels, specific panel observers, who are experienced staff members or members of the Research Councils and experienced academics, participate in the panel meetings. They do not speak or intervene but take written notes as they observe the process in formal, financial or gender terms. These observations aim to improve the process. In case of the SRC, the observations are collected systematically from all panels and reported to the Research Councils, and may lead to various adjustments and improvements of the panel work. One panel observer of SRC explained the role as an SRC panel observer as follows:

“For each round of evaluations for all the evaluation panels we have members from the Scientific Councils that are sitting during the meetings of the panels to observe, and also see to the requirements in terms of fairness, in terms of discussion that all the guidelines that we give to the reviewers are followed, that the conflict of interest is respected, that there are no members who take, you know, shifting the balance towards one side or the other, so that it is fair and respectful discussions, that they are also in terms of the main, how to say the main point that should be evaluated is about quality, but also we have the requirement and the duty to see that the gender balance is respected and that there are no differences and that everybody is having a good and fair evaluation.” (A, observer)

Furthermore, in the SRC, external reviewers may additionally be used in case the panel does not cover the necessary expertise area for an application.

4 EVALUATION IN PRACTICE AND POTENTIAL GENDER BIAS RISKS

In this section, three main topics in respect to potential gender bias are discussed: what is assessed (excellence), how the assessment is done (panel dynamics) and how the final decisions are made.

4.1 Excellence criteria

The way in which formal criteria for assessing excellence are applied in practice is a core element of the assessment process. Even with clear, well-defined formal criteria and instructions on how to assess applications, assessing excellence in practice faces challenges. In our fieldwork, we learned that even when the criteria were clearly defined by the RFO, various challenges and questions arise, like which criteria are most relevant, how to find a common ground on the understanding of scientific excellence in

interdisciplinary panels or whether individual reviewers use the assessment scales differently. Whether and how gender is inscribed in the process gives information about risks of gender bias in practice.

4.1.1 *Formal criteria and scales*

For analysing how panels apply excellence in practice we need to go back to the formal criteria that RFOs have defined. The criteria in the five RFOs are structured similarly as they basically address two aspects of the application – the applicant (lead researcher, principal investigator = PI) and the proposal (proposed research project). Some RFOs define the weight between the two aspects, like 40 % of the total for the merits and CV of the applicant and 60 % for the scores for the project proposal (SRC and NCN). In the SFI call, scores for the PI were weighted with 30 % and the proposal with 70 %, but this is different for emerging investigators (new applicants), with 10 % vs. 90 %. In funding schemes for early career researchers, the proposal for the project is usually attributed more importance than the merits of the PI.

In some RFOs, criteria are added for other dimensions, e.g. impact. Nevertheless, excellence criteria are fine-tuned differently in each RFO context and funding scheme under focus, bringing in indicators for a specific purpose of the funding scheme, like internationalisation in a mobility programme (NCN and SRC) or mentoring in a career development programme (FWF).

We found that the assessment scales differ between the RFOs, but also within one and the same RFO or funding scheme, different scales can be used for different criteria.

At SRC, scientific quality (not excellence) of an application is assessed, based on four basic criteria: (1) scientific quality of the proposed research; (2) novelty and originality; (3) merits of the applicant (all three assessed on a seven-point grading scale); (4) feasibility; and for the IPD mobility grant also (5) internationalisation and (6) research environment (all three assessed on a three-point grading scale). Scientific quality is given most importance, followed by novelty and originality, and then the merits of the applicant. Internationalisation is given more importance in assessing the applications than feasibility.

In the NCN SONATA call, the project assessment constitutes 60 % of the total assessment of an application. Project assessment involves: scientific quality of the research project (30 %), which is evaluated according to a score from 0 (poor) to 5 (excellent); potential impact of the research project (15 %), which is evaluated according to a score from 0 (low) to 3 (high); and feasibility of the research project (15 %), which is evaluated on a scale from 0 (low) to 3 (high). The remaining 40 % is constituted by one single criterion, namely qualifications and scientific achievements of the PI, scored on a scale from 0 (poor) to 5 (excellent).

FWF has remote reviewers use a five-point grading scale to assess seven criteria for which guiding questions are provided: (1) innovation and originality; (2) quality of the proposed research; (3) approach and feasibility; (4) qualifications of the PI; (5) ethics and gender; (6) contribution to the career development of the PI and the suitability of the mentor; (7) suitability of the research institute for implementing the planned project; and (8) overall evaluation. According to the purpose of the funding scheme, also the mentor is assessed. In the panel meeting, these criteria are partly picked up, while the focus is on commenting on the remote reviews.

At SFI and SRDA, excellence of the PI and proposal were assessed by remote reviewers, while panel members only discussed the fairness of the remote reviewers' assessment of the applications. SFI panel

members were strictly asked not to refer to the (excellence of the) PI or the research proposal. SFI panel members adjust the scores suggested by the remote reviewers, focussing on the consistency of scores provided by the three reviewers, the consistency between written feedback and scores and how the rebuttal from applicants has been taken up. In the SRDA GC 2020 call, remote reviewers assessed the excellence of PIs, the research team and the applications, whereas panel members, as rapporteurs of the remote reviews, mainly checked whether the two remote reviews per application did not differ too much and were assessed fairly or whether all excellence/assessment criteria were appropriately taken into account. In the panels primarily commenting on remote reviews (SFI, SRDA), excellence criteria were not discussed as much as in panels directly assessing proposals.

All RFOs have developed guiding questions or sub-indicators for each assessment criterion to support the panel members' evaluation of the applications. These are also available for the applicants and might be used as guidance when preparing applications. Providing guiding questions to reviewers as well to applicants can be seen as an element of transparency.

In the last few years, RFOs have fine-tuned their criteria and some have increasingly adopted them according to the DORA principles (FWF, NCN, SFI). How this impacts the assessment in practice is discussed below.

4.1.2 *Assessment of applicants*

As far as the criteria discussed for assessing the application are concerned, it is worth noting that we mainly use interview data indicating in which way panel members speak about the criteria applied (quotes), but also 'micro'-observation data, when keywords were noted in observations.

The fieldwork confirmed that for assessing the excellence of the PI two criteria are key: publications and grants.

Publications, impact factor, grants

Publications are the core criterion that was discussed in respect to the applicant's excellence. Having an excellent publication track record seemed to be crucial for being granted. In panels that we could observe, as the SFI panels, we could witness how this was verbalised: Panel members phrased it as "*strong publication record*" or "*excellent publications*" or contrary, noted that a PI lacks excellent publications, has "*no really good paper*" or "*lacks last author papers*".

Further, grants were discussed when assessing a PI's excellence, seeing them as proof for excellence: In the observed panels, applicants were portrayed as "*outstanding... a jewel for [the country]*", which was directly linked to being "*heavily funded*" or as "*strong applicant, a well-known person in the field*" and it was remarked that the person has an "*ongoing ERC Grant*". PIs were also discussed by having "*no funding track record*", "*no grants*", "*only two grants yet*" or "*small funds*".

While this traditional use of excellence criteria was prevalent, we also observed tendencies to question or adjust them. In FWF panels we observed how applicants who have no outstanding publications were approved for funding. Panel members argued that an applicant was "*not having such a strong track record looking at number of publications and citations*" (B, panel member, observation), but then also clearly

stated that this proposal should be funded. They focussed on the applicant's potential when arguing that the listed number of publications "*is promising*". Further, a panel member argued that the PI's stronger involvement in science communication makes up for the lack of recent publications. Another panellist explicitly pointed out the value of an applicant's work for the scientific community and science communication – these were perceived as equivalently relevant for excellence as publications, fostering a broader excellence concept. This illustrates that principles of the DORA declaration are partly applied by some panel members, while no specific reference was made to these guidelines or a more comprehensive discourse on broadening excellence.

We also found that the practice to use impact factors and top-ranked journals for assessing excellence was questioned by some panel members:

"I got a bit annoyed by the general consensus which seemed to me that the excellence of the candidate was only being evaluated based on whether or not somebody had a high-impact publication and I think that's very bad thing, there are too many factors influencing whether or not a paper or manuscript ultimately ends up in a high-impact journal and high-impact journal like being one of the top tier journals, I don't think that that reflects scientific quality." (A, panel member)

The informant pointed out that impact factors are not the decisive factor that informs about the quality of a scientific paper. In particular, in funding schemes for early career researchers, as was the case here, this seems an unrealistic interpretation of excellence. Another panel member, however, argued that in Swedish panels, publication history and impact factor were described as "*hard currency*" in the evaluation of excellence (A, panel member).

In panels which reviewed the assessment provided by remote reviewers, an additional layer was added: Portraying an applicant as an excellent researcher was also linked to the style of the written assessment by remote reviewers. A panel member stated "*I like that there are words in like ... 'high' or 'superb'*" or discussed the reviews they described by having "*no enthusiastic feedback*" (B, panel members, observation). These arguments point to an understanding of the excellent scientist as a genius, but also take for granted that some remote reviewers highlight their assessment using (almost) exaggerated language.

How gender is inscribed in the assessment of the scientific output is complex. When observing panel meetings, we were able to directly listen to the words used to discuss merits and could observe how some panel members referred to gendered notions of excellence, arguing that a female PI has no last author papers or no funding track record. It was also pointed out that "*she is occupied with organisational tasks and therefore has a weak CV*" (B, panel member, observation). One panel member argued that a female applicant did not have an ERC grant, whereas we observed that this standard was never raised for a male applicant (B, panel member, observation). A panellist remarked how what counts as merit is different in different fields, what publications matter, for example, adding that "*sure there are gender issues here as well*", without specifying further (A, panel member).

In most RFOs, the h-index still plays a crucial role when assessing publications: "*In the end what matters is scientometrics [h-index] ...*" (E, panel member). Especially for panel members not specialised in the scientific topic, it is challenging to assess the scientific output of the PI and the research team that can be brought to

the project (*"The problem is that we are so specialised now that basically every application is out of our research topic"* (E, panel member)).

Further, SRDA panel members reported that they use the h-index as they do not fully trust the information provided in the proposal; for this, they google the applicant's h-index and check *"whether they are generally able to produce such papers of such quality which they [state in the application]"* (E, panel member). This is information, as one interviewee stated, that one *"can really evaluate"* (E, panel member), even when not having the specialised thematic knowledge for the project. Also, panel members from RFOs which have not signed DORA, stated that there is a need for clearer rules for how to assess this information in a better and fair way.

'New' excellence

Reforming excellence criteria is part of an ongoing discourse most RFOs are involved in. As stated above, some RFOs have formally signed the DORA declaration, but, again, implementation in practice differs. From our case studies, SFI can be considered as a pioneer, having already implemented a new CV format – the so-called narrative CV. This encourages applicants to report scientific outcomes in a broader sense and to report other merits as well. Also, assessment indicators and instructions have been changed, putting less importance on the quantity of publications and more on their quality in terms of innovativeness and impact. In the FFP2020-call, SFI remote reviewers were asked to use a broader set of indicators for assessing excellence in a more *"holistic manner"* (SFI 2020) and to avoid the h-index metrics.

When asked in the interviews how this worked in practice, reviewers pointed out that in several scientific fields, careers are heavily built on publications which prove an applicant's ability to realise a research project properly. As mentioned above, this assumed 'proof' seems particularly relevant when the proposal is outside the reviewer's expertise. Not being allowed to check the h-index means that this reference is lacking. Thus, reviewers argued that they check the self-reported information in the narrative CV by using Google Scholar or Scopus. They argued that looking up the applicant's track record as well as the h-index enables them to better trust the applicant and to feel safe that this is the right person to be granted.

Further we found that grants were discussed when assessing the PI's excellence, now using other evaluators' assessment as reference.

Some reviewers argued that the narrative CV is a promising concept and that reporting qualitatively about applicants' career achievements could provide a better picture about their potential. In this way, the new format has *"a potential to question the 'rules of the game'"* (C, remote reviewer). Some SFI reviewers pointed out that having implemented a narrative CV makes it much easier to really ascertain whether an applicant has the capacities to run a project successfully as now more activities can be reported, also from outside academia.

From a gender perspective, however, new challenges for a fair assessment might emerge: Qualitative reporting and even assessing more qualitative information is open for bias. An SFI reviewer (C, remote reviewer) pointed out that she perceived female applicants in general to be more modest and men to be more self-confident and that these aspects might become more relevant in the narrative CV. In SRC, some

informants argued that this risk might emerge, whereas others denied this. However, when using more qualitative formats, RFOs need to be aware of this risk.

In RFOs having signed the DORA principles, giving up the h-index was intensely discussed. For NCN, according to staff members, this was to “*improve the evaluation system*”, explaining that NCN “*would really like to avoid any impact factors and stuff like that*”. One informant, however, pointed out some emerging challenges for the panel and how to get all panel members to change their minds: “*Because it [the panel] has to change the mind of the experts [i.e., the panel members], that they shouldn’t look at it as the quantity but first should go to quality*”. This involved, for example, considering the quality of the journal and, for example, give fewer points to articles published in MDPI journals (D, panel chair). The interviews with panel members and panel chairs reflected these difficulties with implementing a shift in focus when assessing track record and publications. Relying on numerical measures was seen as both problematic but also as efficient for comparing lots of proposals:

“With so many proposals, you have to stick to certain criteria when you evaluate the proposal because otherwise you are lost. And then I think, to be honest, I would say this is very much biased toward the evaluation of the publication record. Because it’s easy to measure. Because we see if it’s a good publication or a publication in a journal with a high impact factor, etc. And then the citations for example.” (D, panel chair)

Interestingly, in all RFOs that have signed DORA, it was observed or reported that the h-index and the journal impact factor are still included in the discussion by some panel members.

Additional criteria

Becoming independent from the PhD supervisor or a mentor is crucial for an early career researcher to be able to prove their own capacities. Accordingly, the applicant’s relation to the supervisor or mentor was discussed and remote reviewers were criticised for not noticing that the “*applicant is way too depending on seniors*” (C, panel member, observation). In another case it was argued that this PI seemed to have her (sic!) mentor’s ideas (C, observation). To identify the PI’s own contribution is seen as a challenge:

I think the bar should be somewhere else in terms of excellence of the application. That’s also difficult to assess because it’s not always possible to put your finger on whether the application sparks from the candidate’s own ideas or whether it was their own piece of work or whether [it] originated in the host institution. (A, panel member).

When assessing “internationalisation” as a criterion in a mobility call, a panellist wondered “*what are we really grading here*” (A, panel member). This panellist had observed differences between invitation letters from host institutions, which range from formal matter-of-fact letters, without any ‘value’ words, to ones with enthusiastic invitations and positive characterisations of the applicant, and reflected that it may matter how the applicant gets in touch with the host university, which is why the networking ability matters.

(International) mobility was discussed as gendered precondition for excellence: One panel member argued that having an evaluation criterion which included an emphasis on ‘international recognition’ has gendered consequences:

“The best candidate, not all, but I would risk saying that more frequently, a very good candidate is a man and not a woman. What makes the difference probably is their mobility and the fact that they start working with other groups outside Poland. That might be related to gender bias, but it’s a cultural thing. As an evaluator, I’m not saying that the guy is better because he’s a guy. It’s just because he has a better CV.” (D, panel member)

This meant that the excellent applicant more often could turn out to be a man rather than a woman.

Also, in respect to support structures, gender differences were pointed out. When asking panel members how they see gender equality linked to scientific excellence, many panellists were hesitant and found this a very difficult question to answer, but rather made references to activities of networking and positioning oneself in the academic world.

“Yeah, I do see that they [gender equality and scientific excellence] relate to each other, ... maybe it could be that young men are encouraged to network and make contacts in beforehand with the place that they are applying to ... the streets are paved for them in some way or it is just in their system that they think they are entitled to talk about themselves as being excellent or like I should go to Oxford.” (A, panel member)

4.1.3 Assessing the research project

Originality and novelty

When discussing the research project, originality and novelty were a criterion discussed, in some cases also a formal criterion. At SRDA it was particularly stressed that the originality/novelty of the project idea plays an important role when assessing the excellence of a research project. Asked about the most important factors that make an application an excellent one, almost all SRDA interviewees strongly pointed out first, without hesitating, the originality or the novelty of the research idea:

“For me it’s novelty, it should be novel, it should be something that has not been done that has not been analysed before, that’s absolutely crucial so that is one thing, and it should make sense.” (E, panel member)

The novelty aspect was emphasised as a key aspect of an excellent proposal: *“The most important thing is the application that it’s novel and well-written. [...] It has to have a novel idea but it also has to be well thought out.”* (D, panel member). One panel chair emphasized the importance of having gender balanced panels due to the different perspectives of women and men. The chair here pointed out that women and men in panels favoured different topics:

“Men like to have topics related to competition, achievement of goals, finance, profits, and so on. And if it comes to more social aspects and environmental aspects, I don’t know, employee well-being, they say: ‘it’s a stupid topic’, right? Or at least a topic that will not provide any good or is not very promising for publications, or that this is a topic that will not be an efficient use of money.” (D, panel chair)

This quote also illustrates that topics are favoured which are understood to likely have a demanded output, *“the potential for publishing this”* (D, panel chair).” It was highlighted that to be successful in a

panel (mostly composed of members with different scientific backgrounds), the innovativeness of a research idea needs to be highlighted in a broader context so it becomes understandable for all panel members:

“That is maybe our biggest challenges, to really explain why we find this idea so novel or intriguing or whatsoever, and that seems to be the major obstacle for many of us, so because we are so into it, it is so given, it is such a, of course it is the most interesting in the world for you, but for me as an outsider it might not be the most crucial thing in my daily life...” (A, panel chair)

Feasibility

The feasibility and proper methodology of proposals were frequently referred to, highlighting cases where a research approach seemed to be ‘overambitious’: In a panel we observed (B, observation), this argument was used to reject a proposal on one occasion, at another time it was argued that overambition is no problem as the remote reviewers had been very positive. In general, the feasibility of a project is closely linked to the applicant. Panel members assess *“whether this particular principal investigator has the capabilities to reach the goal”* (D, panel chair).

The research environment was another factor that played a role when discussing excellence of the research project. In particular in STEM fields, it was argued that the quality of the infrastructure in the host institution is a crucial argument when deciding if a proposal should get funded – both technical infrastructure but also personal capabilities as well educated and experienced people are needed to support an applicant to run the project.

In this respect, an NCN staff member identified a risk of bias when assessing the capabilities of the applicants to implement the project. According to this staff member, this criterion was prone to be misunderstood as the intention was to ask the reviewer to assess the institutional rather than the individual capabilities.

Reference to a broader understanding of excellence, for example to social impact, an indicator flagged in the guideline for SFI applicants as *“research outputs that support societal and/or public service”* (SFI without year, 4), was rarely made. An FWF Board member rejected societal impact as an element of excellence in the context of FWF: *“I don’t think that society impact should play a role. That is one of the principals of those RFOs funding basic science”* (B, panel member, observation).

4.1.4 Evaluating excellence in specific contexts: interdisciplinary and international panels

The complexity of assessing excellence also increases when multidisciplinary panels are in place, and when proposals to each panel are handed in from a wide range of disciplines. Interviewees commented on how this made evaluation of excellence of the research plan and of applicants more complicated and less clear, as one panel member concluded: *“There is like no strong absolute level in judging the quality of scientific work right, so this comes out clearly.”* (A, panel member)

The view that scientific quality and excellence are discipline-related was taken up by several interviewees as well as by panel chairs in multidisciplinary panels, as one chair pointed out:

“It is hard to tell what is scientific quality or what is novelty, for instance, because novelty it could be novel within my field, if I’m in field x, and then a scholar in field z might say, we have been doing this for decades. So yes, this is quite challenging ... a carefully written application that is readable to many, because you have to take in consideration that it is everything from [listing disciplines represented in the panel], it should be interesting for the readers, not for you [applicant].” (A, panel chair)

Similarly, a panel member put it like this: Excellence is *“something that I reflected is different between disciplines”* (A, panel member). For this panel member as a Humanities scholar, excellence means the novelty of the research idea, connections to the research field, renewal concerning research discussion and having some kind of empirical material. The interviewee explained having realised in the panel negotiations that other panel members put more emphasis on methods and research design, whereas this interviewee emphasised the research idea, context, theoretical and analytical framework as well as renewing the research field, and was not as stringent about the methods.

Applying standards in a different manner was also discussed in respect to how metrics in mixed panels are applied (SRDA). Moreover, when panel members come from different scientific disciplines of one scientific field (e.g. Technical Science Council, Social Science Council, Natural Science Council), it was reported that they often followed very different citation, publication and scientific output disciplinary conventions. A certain h-index may be valued highly in one scientific sub-discipline, but low in another of the same panel. It was argued that, for example within Social Sciences panels, an h-index of 10 is considered high in Economic Sciences, whereas in Law an h-index of 2 is acceptable. Panel members need to deal with these different standards, involving the risk that applicants are not assessed against their appropriate standards.

It was pointed out in the interviews and already described in chapter 3.2 that having international panels is, on the one hand, understood as a request for having a certain assessment quality and to avoid nepotism. On the other hand, having international panels brings some challenges as it further complicates the assessment of excellence. When panel members come from very different scientific traditions not only due to their disciplinary background, but also due to their national science context, certain traditions are perceived as more important than others. This involves, for example, the relevance of mobility and previous postdoc visits or other examples of internationalisation. Academic career paths differ among countries and those differences might influence the panel members’ expectations of applicants and *“what is expected from a CV at each career stage”* (D, panel member). Panel members described discussions during the panel meetings when different views on this were discussed, and explained that these were based on disciplinary and contextual differences.

Agreeing on how to apply the evaluation criteria concerning qualifications and scientific achievements of the PI was also explained to be challenging in the international panels. For this, support from RFO staff was considered beneficial. In case of NCN panels, the participation of NCN Coordinators was described as indispensable by several of the panel members and panel chairs: *“That’s why it’s good to have the Coordinator of the panel that actually knows the academic context well and has the ability to explain what is expected from a CV at each career stage”* (D, panel member).

4.1.5 *Calibrating excellence: how to apply scores and criteria*

RFOs partly have formal generic specifications in place which specify how scores should be applied. For example, the FWF defines ‘excellent’ applications, for which *“funding is highly recommended”* in the following way: *“The proposed research project is among the best 5 % in its field worldwide. It has the potential to break new ground and make a major contribution to generating new knowledge. The applicant and the researchers involved have outstanding qualifications by international standards”* (FWF 2018).

Panel members explained in the interviews that in some panels the way to apply criteria was discussed and calibration practices could be reported on. In panels of other RFOs, this was not reported as an element at the start of a panel meeting. In interviews with NCN panel members, different aspects of calibration were salient. One important informal practice during the initial stages of the panel meetings in NCN was to agree on what excellence is and how to identify it. The purpose of these calibration discussions was to align different interpretations and applications of the scores and criteria. This process involved intense discussions between the panel members, and sometimes also the panel chair, about the assessment criteria and how to apply them and to weigh the scores. Thus, before the panel members could agree on the scoring and assessment of each individual application, they sought to agree on how to use the abstract numeric scales and how to apply the descriptions of the assessments such as ‘poor’ or ‘excellent’ to the concrete applications. They also discussed what can be assessed as scientific output: *“At the beginning, we had this discussion about how we evaluate the publication record, especially with this open access. The first three proposals I think took us much longer”* (D, panel chair). Other NCN panel members described this calibration practice as less formal and less explicit, but something that developed gradually during the panel discussions: *“It’s more like a scale you’re getting after, let’s say, 10 or 15 proposals. Let’s say we are working on the proposals and we are making the rules as we are working and at one point when we have let’s say, judged 10 or 15 proposals, it’s more like a non-written agreement between us”* (D, panel member).

As a result of the calibration process, the panel members realised that some of them had constantly used higher scores than others – although their evaluation and assessments of the applications were very similar. Reflecting on the abstract meanings enabled panel members to adjust their scoring to the overall level in the panel: *“I realised that I was the worst [lowest] scorer of the whole. [...] I completely changed my way of reviewing proposals”* (D, panel member).

That grading scales are applied differently by reviewers was taken up by many panellists in the SRC. One SRC panellist described this as a surprise when starting work in the panel: *“The fact that applications were rated in such discrepant way between different members of the panel, that is something that I hadn’t expected.”* (A, panel member).

An interesting aspect on age differences was brought up by an NCN panel member, arguing that *“younger people are evaluating more severely than the senior people”* (D, panel member). Age was also mentioned at SRC: When trying to come to an agreement, a chair had observed that seniors who are more confident in their reviewer role may adjust their scoring more easily after discussions in the panel, whereas junior panellists who are more insecure have been observed to do this less. Another SRC panellist explained how panellists graded the applications *“a little differently”*, meaning they used the scales differently. The panellist said this was already brought up in the introductory briefing meeting that this would happen, but

without elaborating. The informant described this as a systemic problem. Panellists with a more generous mode of grading were prevalent in this panel this round, and after the upgrading and downgrading, the overall grading in the panel became more generous. This interviewee had given four (out of seven) as the highest grade, but observed that it corresponded to somebody else's grade seven. The result of this was, according to the informant, that those who had been more strictly graded up and those who had been very generous graded down when the panel calibrated the scores. The informant commented how most panellists in this panel thought that seven, the highest grade, should only be reserved to a "new Bourdieu, Butler or Foucault". As a result of the discussion, no sevens were awarded (as a final grade) to anybody in this panel. This comment on grading concerned all sub-criteria, not only the overall grade. The panellist also remarked that one could identify fellow panellists by their grading style, with some variation.

Another SRC panel member described how the calibration of grades took place in practice:

"In some cases from the beginning we had very different grading from one putting 1 and one putting 7, that happened on different parts, but during the discussion you realize, okay I misunderstood that or you saw things or it wasn't that kind of harsh, and then very often there was a person in the middle so we had [grades] a seven and a three and a one [given on one application], but often we were quite close and we also suggested a ranking so from the 19 [applications] I read I had to put them in a ranking [order] even if they [some of them] had the same grading in total." (A, panel member)

Several SRC panellists said they never used the top or bottom grades, which they had observed could mean a drawback:

"I realised that I never used, when I started...I never used the top and the bottom [grade]. And some of the others were the same. And that was a drawback for all that I assessed because they came down [in ranking] directly. And that was something, that if you have been there for years, you know that I will put seven up and one down, but you want to make sure. From European Research Council we had a discussion about this. Be a bit humble, don't put up the highest and the lowest [grade] to give a freedom of discussion." (A, panel member)

RFOs have different forms of quality assurance for the reviewers' scores in place: SFI panels only discuss the quality of remote reviews, the FWF office comments on the remote reviews in its Office Suggestion and later the panel as well. In NCN, the remote reviewers' assessments and scoring are discussed during the second panel meeting. While calibration practices are appreciated in NCN panels, they are lacking for NCN remote reviewers: As this calibration process was emphasised as being an essential panel practice, it was also acknowledged that it was a problem that the external experts were not part of this. This even resulted in that part of the external experts' evaluation being disregarded: "We kind of ignored the [remote] reviewers' views on this because they hadn't been part of this [the calibration process]" (D, panel member).

At SRDA, it is the panel's task to assess the quality of remote reviews, also by comparing scores between different remote reviewers, which is why this kind of quality assurance can be seen as a calibration practice as well.

Another example of calibration across gradings could be observed in FWF and SRC panel meetings: To be able to prepare a ranking list which is as detailed as possible, the chair and other members introduced more

fine-grained informal grading in some panels. When FWF panellists talked about applications scored with A minus, it was stated that an application has *“a very short minus”* or *“This application has a longer minus than before”* (B, panel members, observation), which helps ranking the applications. A similar practice could be found in some SRC panels, which divided applications scored with a relatively high grade 5 into three sub-groups, for instance applications scored with 5 into 5, 5 minus and 5 plus, to facilitate the final ranking.

4.1.6 Gender in research content and innovation (GiRI)

Following the EU requirement in Horizon Europe to integrate the sex and gender dimension in research and innovation (GiRI) in all research proposals (or arguing why it is not relevant), made GiRI an element of excellence that is now assessed in some case RFOs. Remote reviewers and panel members now have to assess the incorporation of the sex and gender dimension in applications of their respective research field. To support this work, most of the GRANteD case study RFOs have provided instructions or guidelines to facilitate addressing gender in the research and innovation content. For instance, SFI has provided guidelines for applicants as well as for remote reviewers, and already since 2016, staff has been trained on GiRI.

Our fieldwork provided insights into how remote reviewers and panel members from different RFOs have dealt with this request in practice. They described their experiences and perceptions and gave feedback on the implementation of this policy.

In some RFOs, members had argued that it was already demanding to push this policy within the RFO as some RFO representatives did not necessarily understand the need for it. But it was also argued that linking excellence to the incorporation of the sex and gender dimension is crucial as *“RFOs establish standards how research needs to be done”* (B, staff). RFO staff members observed that it takes time for remote reviewers and panel members to get used to this policy and to progress in applying it: *“At the beginning it was a formal thing and now it is a thing that they take into account for the decision.”* (B, staff)

When observing FWF panels, this relevance was, however, not obvious. Only in very few negotiations did we observe that reference was made to gender in research. For example, for a proposal in the Social Sciences, reviewers pointed out that gender was addressed as a non-binary concept, and when discussing an application in the Life Sciences, the composition of a mice sample was highlighted as sex-balanced.

SFI panels did not discuss GiRI neither (they only discussed the quality of remote reviews). SFI remote reviewers of the FFP call 2020 were instructed for the first time more precisely about GiRI, namely to *“focus only on the relevance of gender in their research content and innovation”* (SFI 2020). This specific request to focus on content (and not on a gendered team composition), however, did not seem easy to understand and to put in practice. Remote reviewers showed difficulties in distinguishing between gender in research content and gender in research teams. When discussing GiRI, this was mostly linked to the representation of women in panels, in teams or in samples. Some reviewers argued that GiRI did not play any role as they reviewed only very few applications from female applicants, linking GiRI to the representation of female applicants (lower number of female applicants as SFI only funds STEM fields). Reviewers working in countries with a strong tradition in affirmative actions (e.g. US) referred to the representation of women in research teams specifically, arguing that they are used to take gender into account by including more

women into research teams. For them, gender balance in teams (and a better inclusion of other underrepresented groups in science) is a well-known and well-practiced policy.

In contrast, awareness and knowledge about how to operationalise the policy was not developed yet among SFI reviewers. This might be due to the fact that FFP proposals come from Life Sciences and STEM fields where the relevance of the gender dimension is less obvious than in Humanities or Social Sciences, and the discourse on GIRI is less advanced. Reviewers referred to their own research arguing that gender is irrelevant there, naming Mathematics or Material Sciences (rock samples) as examples. Others stated that they had not thought about gender in research in their discipline before, arguing: *“Typically in my area of research we don't think about that at all, so that made me think for a while”* (C, remote reviewer).

When asked how applicants had considered GiRI, remote reviewers of the SFI reported that often GiRI was not addressed at all. They were not surprised that this demand was only picked up by very few applicants. And they did not question when applicants denied the gender relevance in their proposal or when applicants argued that addressing gender would lead to a different project.

When it comes to the assessment of GIRI, it was argued that the reviewer's task is only to assess whether what is included is reliable. The applicant's contribution is perceived as *“helpful for the assessment”* (C, remote reviewer) as the applicant is the expert on the relevance of gender in their topic, who then has to decide if, where and how to integrate the gender dimension in the research proposal. If an applicant does not pick up on the issue, then the entry in the SFI review form simply states that the gender dimension was not addressed.

When reflecting on the GIRI policy in general, remote reviewers also rated it as an innovative and pioneer measure. It was argued that the SFI request to assess GiRI (scoring and providing a written review) is a chance for reviewers to learn, to become more gender-aware personally and to take this awareness home to be applied in their home institutions. This learning perspective was also stressed for applicants, and remote reviewers pointed out that the GiRI requirement is a chance for applicants to develop a broader research perspective and to advance their gender competence.

In short, our fieldwork revealed some challenges that remote reviewers and panel members face when they need to assess the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content. Panels rarely discuss GiRI. Most remote reviewers lack awareness and understanding of the concept, sometimes confusing sex and gender content with gender team composition. What is particularly lacking is an understanding for how GiRI is linked to the concept of excellence and why the quality of research benefits from taking the sex and gender dimension into account. The challenges might increase when, in the near future, evaluators will be asked to take an intersectional perspective in addition to the sex and gender dimension, referring to inequalities related to other social dimensions such as ethnicity, socio-economic background or disabilities.

Providing support for how to assess GiRI in field-specific approaches and general gender knowledge is needed; the exact form of support needed has to be further explored.

4.2 Panel dynamics

4.2.1 Briefing panel members and introducing them to panel work

Prior to the panel meetings, panel members of all five RFOs are briefed regarding the panel work and their role in the panel via different information channels. When new panel members join panels, they receive guidelines from the respective RFO regarding the panel work and their role inside the panel. One SRDA panel member told the GRANteD team in the interview that additionally to the information received, they browsed the SRDA website for additional information or contacted the SRDA directly. If GE policies are in place in the RFO, the guidelines also refer to them. For example, the guidelines for the IPD that SRC sent out to the panel members describe not only panel work, but also explain gender equality policies of SRC.

Additionally, the FWF provides gender training for new FWF Board members; SRC briefs the panel members using introductory sessions and all panel members of the SFI panels have to watch an anti-bias video provided by the RFO prior to the panel meetings.

The remote reviewers also receive guidelines regarding the remote reviewing process, the assessment criteria and their role. However, they seldom receive additional training on the general procedure or on GE topics (if any are in place). In FWF, the possibility of conducting such training is also discussed for remote reviewers, but is not implemented yet.

At the start of panel meetings, the panel chairs or project managers normally shortly introduce the role and formal settings of the panel (e.g. time to discuss proposal, use of gender-neutral language, etc.). Here, the specifics of the respective funding programme are also referred to (e.g. the FWF Board chair pointed out that ESPRIT is a “*women’s promotion programme*”) and what needs to be taken care of. Panel members of the SRDA panels also pointed out that panel chairs are available for answering the newcomers’ questions.

4.2.2 Working atmosphere and discussion culture in panels

In general, the social dynamics in the panels across all RFOs were commented on in positive terms by the informants, describing them as friendly, constructive, cooperative, pragmatic and/or fair. Furthermore, most of the interviewed panel chairs and members perceived the meetings as well structured, even though almost all panel meetings of the funding programmes in focus took place online due to the COVID-19 pandemic and its restrictions. The participants had to adapt to new conditions. In this respect, SFI is an exception since their panel meetings had already taken place in a hybrid format before the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, SFI had already gained experience in handling technical issues during meetings, sticking to more strict speaking rules. Virtual SFI panels and virtual FWF panels observed had an atmosphere that is best characterised as efficient with structured discussions. Similarly, this was also the case in the two observed FWF panels, but when the panel finally met face to face again, the atmosphere was livelier, people chatted, so that sometimes discussions were difficult to follow.

The main aim of the panel meetings was to go through every application that was a subject of the meeting and to come to an agreement together as a panel. The NCN panels in the first round discuss all incoming and formally accepted applications. Reaching decisions on these applications (e.g. proposing to be funded/not funded or to be sent to the next step/not sent to the next step) was a key aspect of the panel

meetings. These decisions were also influenced by discussion dynamics. One panel member of the NCN SONATA funding programme described the panel dynamics observed as follows:

“In the panel meeting, we need to agree on the final mark. Everything is possible at this moment, to be honest. If there is a huge disagreement and you are running against time, there isn’t unlimited time for these discussions, if you have a very strong opinion, you will voice it, but then it truly depends on your receptor and on who’s managing the meeting. I don’t have any problem saying what I think and I will voice it and I will fight it until a certain limit” (D, panel member)

So, actually, ‘fighting for an application’ is a frequent practice. In the observed panels a chair asked directly *“Are you ready to fight for your position?”* (C, chair, observation) and a panel member signalled willingness for a quick solution, offering *“I do not want to fight for this one, I am happy to go with your assessment”* (C, panel member, observation).

In the interviews with the panel chairs and members across all RFOs, it was emphasised that *“making one’s voice heard clearly and vehemently”* and therefore taking sides for or against a certain application may influence discussions considerably and steer them in a certain direction. Especially, expressing one’s opinion enthusiastically for the scientific issue under discussion can develop an enormous power in discussions, winning other panel members over. This phenomenon was addressed in one of the SRC panel member interviews. A relatively new panellist had noticed that what really made a difference in discussion on how to grade an application was if one person in the panel stepped forward and said: *“I think this is brilliant”, “I think this is very good”* (A, panel member). The panellist argued that what really makes a difference is if one person *“really defends it”*, and how, if other panel members point out weaknesses, there is someone who consistently steps forward and says: *“Yes, but this could really move the field and this could really be important in this and this aspect...”*.

In several interviews with panel members of NCN, it was emphasised that evaluating proposals, or at least the panel meetings when these evaluations were discussed, were not completely objective, but rather infused by emotions: *“There are a lot of emotional parts of the brain that are active. To me, it makes sense because these evaluations are not all based on very strict criteria. There are emotions in what we think about science and impact”* (D, panel member).

These quotes illustrate the complex dynamics of negotiations and that it makes a difference by whom and how an application is presented and defended. They also illustrate that there is space for individual assessment and preferences.

In addition, opinions of respected and experienced panel members with a high reputation in their scientific field may have a great weight in panel discussions. One SRDA panellist described it as follows: *“If this woman is very important of course, we have to accept more [her] opinion”* (E, panel member). Even if there are doubts regarding opinions of these respected panel members, one dares not to contradict too much. This unspoken law of paying respect to important and scientifically respected panel members by giving more weight to their opinion can be found more firmly anchored in countries like Slovakia and Poland, where traditional hierarchical societal and social norms are still more persistent.

Another point raised in the interviews was that the personal style of panel members (introvert vs. extrovert), body language as well as communication and rhetoric skills can play a crucial role when engaging in panel discussions. It was made clear by one panel member of the NCN that in their opinion shy, not very talkative panel members may find it more difficult to assert themselves in panel discussions. Not only are some panel members *“more charming”* than others, as this interviewee put it, some are also more articulate and talk more than others, and these variations appeared to influence the meeting dynamics: *“the person with the less loud personality gets muted”* (D, panel member). Especially, during face-to-face panel meetings it may cost quite an effort to protest about something being said by another panel member. Inappropriate and degrading facial expressions (e.g. rolling one’s eyes), loud sighs, or self-confident body language that takes up space may reinforce the hurdle of saying something or even contradicting. Virtual meetings can be beneficial in this respect, as experienced by panel members (see chapter 4.2.4).

During SFI FFP panel meetings, it could be observed that it was not easy for all panel members to get used to the new role of not discussing the quality of applications but the quality of the remote review(er)s. Some regressed to the former reviewer role to comment on applications, and in this case the chair or SFI staff members had to remind panel members not to talk about the applicant or the research proposal (but about reviews only) or to *“justify why reference to proposal is needed”* (C, panel chair). Occasionally, a panel member pointed to the new rule and repeated that *“...our job is to look on quality of reviewers, if the applicants react well and if the reviewers corrected well”* (C, panel member, observation).

4.2.3 Gender dynamics

Most panellists across all RFOs argued in the interviews that gender played a limited role in the panel meetings, if any. Direct reference to gender was mostly made when commenting on applying gender equality measures in practice (e.g. checking for maternity, paternity or parental leaves, re-ranking in terms of underrepresented gender). Overall, panellists said that in their view, scientific excellence does not depend on the gender of the applicants, but on their acquired scientific knowledge and skills. They argued that both men and women can be outstanding scientists in different scientific fields. They emphasised that attention was not being paid to the applicants’ gender or said that they even did not notice gender, that gender was not taken into account and that they, in that sense, were neutral regarding the gender of the applicant. One NCN panellist reported that *“at least for me, gender was never a question or something that would be revisited in a careful way in the ranking list. I don’t remember that being done”* (D, panel member). Or an SRDA panellist said: *“I don’t look at the gender of the principal investigator. I’m not looking even into the number of women or men among the research team, absolutely not”* (E, panel member). Here, we find a practice of ignoring the relevance of gender in the assessment process by arguing that there is no gender relevance or gender bias. Whether and to what extent these responses were influenced by social desirability (Furr 2010), given that the informants were aware that GRANteD is studying gender bias, should also be considered.

In interviews with NCN and SRDA panel members, the existence of gender bias was denied. One NCN panellist stated in this respect: *“To be honest I don’t see any problems with bias because this is so much work, that it’s very hard to even be biased probably”* (D, panel chair), indicating a view that assumes bias being a conscious action rather than something unconscious. Or in the interviews with SRDA panellists, it was underlined that both female and male panellists are regarded just as *“gender-neutral”* rapporteurs who

have the same functions and positions and work objectively and without any gender bias. In line with this practice of ignoring or downplaying the significance of gender due to a lack of gender awareness was the discussion about gender equality measures by the SRDA panellists: Reference was only made to conventional parenthood-related measures like maternity/paternity leave, while more innovative policies like re-ranking were not seen as attractive or relevant to increase gender equality.

When panel members in the interviews recalled gender-related dynamics during panel meetings, they often referred to different working methods, compliance with rules, speaking time or presentation style of certain male or female panellists. These attributions very often mirror stereotypical characteristics of women and men. This can also be observed in RFOs with a longer tradition in gender equality policies. For example, one SRC panellist describes that *“men especially in professional context probably speak a little bit more forcefully about their views you know, stereotyped sort of gender normative thing, women tend to be more, probably better at listening and better at, I don’t know, maybe sort of taking other people’s views into account and reconciling them, whereas men maybe clash a little bit more”* (A, panel member).

One panel member argued that even if panel members believe in old and traditional stereotypes regarding women and men, they would be clever enough not to openly show them. Also, RFO management members stated that in respect to gender *“you really have to be careful what you say”* (B, staff). These examples indicate how social desirability influences overt behaviour not necessarily matching underlying attitudes and assumptions.

Against this background, as most RFOs panellists said in the interviews that in their view gender played a limited role in panel meetings and the assessment of applications, a very interesting aspect emerged from SRC interviews. The chairs and observers who were in charge of implementing the gender equality policies, and staff and observers monitoring the implementation, detailed in their accounts of how and in which phases gender aspects are taken up in the panel work in practice. However, the interviews with SRC rank-and-file panellists gave a more diverse picture. For the panellists, gender paradoxically appeared both as visible and invisible during different phases of panel meetings. There seemed to be some uncertainty among some panellists how and in which conditions gender should be addressed in the panel work. A panellist concluded: *“Gender was not really part of it [discussion of proposals], I think it would have been very difficult I think to have gender influence the results based on how candidates were discussed”* (A, panel member).

Two other panellists similarly explained how they thought gender aspects came in only at the end of the panel work:

“The gender representation was only discussed after we had a draft of the ranking. So, it was at the very end. So, in this case it seemed more of an afterthought. It was not part of the discussion during the day.” (A, panel member)

“At the final decision they are looking at the gender but before that they won’t. I’m now really used to it I think it should be done already when you evaluate it. It was only in the end.” (A, panel member)

“Something around gender was going on in the panel work”, was remarked by one panellist, but they found it difficult to pin down. It was not clear for some panellists what to do if the rankings ended in a strong gender imbalance:

“We also get the information of the application and the gender of the applicant and its provided and the process for VR is you basically assess the applications irrespective of the gender of the applicant... The bigger issue I would say is the guidelines that were provided about what to do are rather vague. It’s not clear to me how we are supposed to actually take action even if it did end up that we gave a lot of, if we ended up in a situation where we had a bunch of male applicants who got higher scores and we were giving disproportionate number of grants to male applicants. I don’t know what we would do about that.” (A, panel member)

Chairs, staff members and observers who participate in panel meetings with an implementation and monitoring function look at the panel discussions from a different angle and therefore also perceive different, subliminal dynamics, which panellists do not necessarily even notice or are aware of. This example of SRC shows the importance of having monitoring structures with a certain accountability to decision-making bodies in place, paying attention not only to applying formal policies but to constructive meeting dynamics as well, even in RFOs that are already experienced with gender equality policies.

SFI is another interesting example when it comes to gender neutrality. SFI strives to create a “gender-neutral” environment during panel meetings by the implementation of certain rules of discussion. Applications were introduced by application ID only and respective applicants were addressed with general terms like “the PI” or “the applicant” in order to give no room to stereotypes. However, the observations showed that giving up the reference to an applicant’s sex/gender and perceiving applications as “gender-neutral” does not come easy to panellists. From time to time, they regressed to old patterns and used personal pronouns in evaluative speech, when underlining positive or negative aspects about the applicants. Then, also gender stereotypes could be read between the lines (e.g. “*she has her mentor’s ideas*”; “*she has not published since...*” versus “*he is a great guy*”, “*he is a young guy, let’s give him a chance*”). Most of the times when sex/gender was raised, the chair or staff members intervened, arguing that the name and sex should not be mentioned and therefore took up a control function. Additionally, the new function of SFI panels also contributed to a more gender-neutral environment and discussion practices during panel meetings. However, gender did play a role across all RFOs when gender equality measures had to be applied, such as maternity/paternity measures, other leave measures as well as re-ranking measures.

For NCN and SRDA, which do not have many formal gender equality policies/measures in place yet, this meant that panellists were specifically asked in the interviews about whether, how and to what extent maternity leave for women was considered when the scientific achievements of the PI were evaluated. Although in both RFOs this was not described as a policy implemented or applied in a consistent manner with clearly formulated criteria, the panel members expressed support for this measure, as it was understood to be ‘fair’ but also an expression of an attitude about “*we have to help her [referring to a woman who is returning to work after extended maternity leave]*” (D, panel member), as one NCN panel member phrased it. In case of the NCN, it was also implied that this was a policy that the panel members did not have to consider, as the application system had already been adjusted for this. However, it is also emphasised in the NCN regulations for proposal evaluation criteria in the SONATA call that, when the panel members evaluate the qualifications and scientific achievements of the PI, any career breaks should be considered. However, this was described as an issue that was raised and that some panel members needed to be reminded about this.

In SRC panels, gender is considered throughout the process. An SRC panel chair with long experience explains that discussing gender issues starts with the sifting phase, which includes monitoring the gender ratio of women and men applicants. If there is a gender imbalance among those suggested to be sifted, the chair and vice-chair need to discuss if there is anything to reconsider, and the observers may help in this. Reviews of the three panel members allocated to each application are then presented for the panel by the rapporteur, followed by the discussion in the panel. In the panel discussion on the final ratings, the panel gets back to gender aspects and a possible re-ranking of applications of the underrepresented gender assessed to be of the same scientific quality.

4.2.4 Implications from the experiences of online meetings during COVID-19

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic almost all panel meetings of the funding calls in focus in GRANteD shifted from being face to face (or hybrid in case of SFI) to digital meetings. Differences between digital meetings and face-to-face meetings were discussed during the interviews with both panel members and with staff. The most prominent theme was that the panel dynamics changed in the digital meetings compared to the face-to-face meetings. Some of the interviewed panel members and panel chairs could compare the panel dynamics during the digital panel meetings with the face-to-face panel meetings before the pandemic and therefore could highlight advantages and disadvantages of the two formats.

The interviews indicated that overall, the chairs, panellists and staff prefer meetings face to face due to various reasons. A key factor in this regard is the social component, which is largely missing in digital meetings. There is no room for informal chats (e.g. in breaks, before/after the meetings), which are regarded as networking opportunities and important for panellists. One SRC panellist summarised it the following way: *“Doing it online was just fine. The only thing we missed out on was having a chit chat with other people [...] when you talk over a coffee, which I think is not particularly important for grading these applications”* (A, panel member).

Furthermore, digital panel meetings do not provide room for lively discussions. They are subject to stricter discussion rules, which may lead to the involvement of fewer panellists when discussing certain applications. The involvement of all the panel members is an important aspect that was difficult to achieve during a digital panel meeting. One NCN panellist states in this respect that *“with panel meetings face-to-face, it’s a very, sometimes even chaotic process, but very energetic in that sense because everyone gets involved, especially in very good proposals. Everyone wants to understand why we like it so much. In virtual environments, it’s flatter. The enthusiasm is flatter”* (D, panel member). It could also be more difficult to protest against something being said by another panel member during a digital panel meeting, where speaking turns are more regulated, and thus it is more difficult to influence the direction of the discussion immediately. After reintroducing face-to-face panels in FWF after a few online meetings, one member stated in respect to the dynamics of discussions: *“We are not yet where we were before”* (B, staff).

However, the geographical distance to the other panellists and screen format are seen as advantages: The fact that the faces of panellists appear as small tiles on the screen in digital meetings could empower shy panellists to raise their voices. An NCN panellist put it the following way: *“I think for shy people, digital meetings are easier because when you talk, you get to talk, and you don’t get to see if someone makes a funny face because they’re too small [on the computer screen]. Sometimes people, the wrong kind of people,*

that try to be oppressive, they use their body language to make people quiet. You can't see that if they're just small screens, they're all the same. So, you get past that thing" (D, panel member). The digital meeting thus became more democratic in a way, disempowering people who would otherwise tend to dominate or influence the discussions with body language, facial expressions or audible sighs and groaning to convey disagreement. Furthermore, another NCN panellist also reported that in their opinion, emotions and, as the informant put it, "*charm*" are harder to transmit in digital meetings ("*you don't feel the charm of someone*" (D, panel chair)). Therefore, digital meetings may in a sense be more objective than face-to-face meetings.

Although most of the informants across all RFOs preferred meetings face to face and acknowledged that there were some problems with digital meetings (also technical and organisational), they also emphasised that the outcome was not affected and that panel work had not been adversely impacted. SFI has even decided to keep the panel meetings digital in the future. Digital meetings are especially convenient for international panels. There is no need to travel to the panel meetings in the respective country, which saves time for panellists, money for the RFOs and – of course, from an ecological point of view – CO₂. Especially women, who still have to reconcile the twin roles of homemaker/caretaker and money-maker more often than men, might be more likely to take on a reviewer function if there is no need to travel.

4.3 Decision-making and re-ranking practices

4.3.1 Final decision-making

After discussing a proposal, FWF panels need to agree on the final grade: For this purpose, the chair summarises the arguments raised by the reporters, (often) checks back with the member(s) of the Executive Board and announces the final grade decision. The grades inform how to proceed with the applications (Grade A proposals are immediately approved for funding, proposals graded with A minus stay in the pool of fundable projects as well as B1 proposals, grade C proposals are rejected by formalised arguments). The chair, supported by Executive Board member(s) has a decisive role.

In SFI context, we find a rather strong role of the two lead reviewers in the panel who introduce the reviews of an application, while here the chair basically supports them in coming to a common decision. As soon as an agreement is achieved to upgrade or downgrade one or more score(s), this information is entered in the IT system and immediately changes the overall score, visible for all participants of the panel meeting. The funding decision suggested by the panel is binding, irrespectively of the scores. After re-ranking (see 5.3), the final funding decision is made by the SFI board, taking into account the available budget.

In the SRC, the applications are reviewed by three panellists, with one of them being the rapporteur. The lowest-rated applications are removed from discussion (sifting). The rapporteur introduces the application shortly to the panel, followed by a panel discussion. The proposed score of the three panellists is discussed and can be adjusted in the discussion (see 4.15). The chair has a facilitating role. When all applications have been rated by the panel, re-ranking of applications of equal scientific quality can take place to reach gender balance. The panel only ranks the applications, the final decision is made by the General Director.

In NCN, the final decision-making about the scoring, assessment and ranking of the applications takes place during the second panel meeting. The second panel meeting thus ends with the panel agreeing on a ranking list of applications, which the Coordinator later presents to the Director, who approves or (possibly but

rarely) disapproves the ranking list. The formal NCN procedure gives the Coordinators the possibility to modify the ranking after consulting with the panel members, even though this was rarely done.

At SRDA, applications for which the remote reviewers assessed the criteria in a similar way and the two rapporteurs agreed on these assessments, are normally quickly dealt with during the panel meetings. Ambiguities in the assessments need more time for discussion and may lead to a change of the average score. Councils may change the average score by a maximum of ± 5 points which needs the consent of an absolute majority of panel members. When occasionally panels decide to change the average score by more than ± 5 points, such a decision must be unambiguously justified, reported to the Bureau of the Agency¹⁵ and the Presidium¹⁶ of the SRDA and is therefore connected with a lot of extra paper and negotiation work with the Bureau of the Agency and the Presidium. Finally, written draft decisions for all approved applications are submitted to the Director of the Agency.

4.3.2 Formal re-ranking policies

Recent research argues that gender-balanced outcomes (same number of grantees or equal success rates) are due to re-ranking at the end and formal policies that encourage panels to re-rank applications according to these targets (Bol et al. 2022). We analyse this policy in detail, first by presenting the formal definition and then discussing how these policies work in practice.

Policies to achieve an intended gender distribution in the funding outcomes – either an equal number of female and male grantees or equal success rates of female and male applicants – are in place in SRC, SFI and in FWF. While having similar gender equality targets, to guarantee that a predefined number or proportion of female applicants is granted, these policies differ broadly in their formal implementation and also in how they are practiced in panels. The FWF target is *“to award at least half of all ESPRIT projects to female principal investigators”* (FWF without year, 17), which implies a re-ranking of applications in case this ‘quota’ is not met in each Board meeting. The SRC guidelines describe re-ranking as a borderline condition to prioritise the underrepresented gender in cases where the scientific quality of the applicants is deemed to be equivalent, and the guidelines also request a gender-balanced number of grantees. Panel members can argue to lift a proposal that has initially been sifted (taken from the group of proposals to be discussed in the panel and considered for funding): *“[...] if somebody wants to lift an application [that had been sifted] for discussion they just have to say, I want to lift that one, they don’t need to argue for it, [...]”* (A, observer). It is noteworthy that in the FWF and SRC panels under focus in our study, only a small number of grants are approved, thus a change of one or two grantees can tilt the gender balance of grantees significantly. For SFI FFP applications the re-ranking is defined as follows: *“When ranking applications, in*

¹⁵ The Bureau of the Agency is the organisation of the SRDA and consists of the director and the director’s office of the SRDA and the following departments: 1) department of projects, 2) department of human resources, 3) department of international cooperation and state aid, 4) department of economics and international operations, 5) control department.

¹⁶ The Agency Presidium is a top expert body of the SRDA. The Presidium of the Agency consists of 13 members, of which twelve members are significant, nationwide respected science and technology experts. The main tasks of the Agency Presidium are: approval of the Agency’s concept of activities; proposal of candidates for the Agency Council members; approval of announcing general calls; approval of criteria for funding of projects; approval of annual activity report and annual economic report (see SRDA homepage: <https://www.apvv.sk/>).

the event of applications receiving the same final score, SFI will give priority to applications from female candidates.”

4.3.3 Practising re-ranking

In the SRC context, re-ranking being practised in the panel meeting was mentioned quite rarely in interviews with panellists. A chair explained the use of re-ranking and who is affected by it:

“Yes, both when I have been in a panel as a member and as Chair [I have experience of re-ranking]. What you do is generally, you will do this for the applications which are around the line, the cut-off line, so a certain number above and a certain number below, I can’t say the actual number, but we do take quite a large part in there, and look at the ones who have essentially the same grade, and there we have the right to lift up an application of an under-represented gender if they have the same grade, but we do have a discussion about this also, and it is still so that scientific quality must still come first ... so this one kind of overrules all the ... So yes, we do make use of this, and this is sort of part of the strategy of the Swedish Research Council.” (A, chair)

SRC panels usually agree on ranking, but in cases where there are very different views, interviewees described some practices to solve the issue: An additional panellist (beyond the norm of three per application) may be asked to perform a quick review, or the panel Chair may intervene and discuss with the assigned reviewers. Another option is that the group of assigned reviewers may talk informally in a coffee break and after this discussion the panel gets back to discussing the proposal. This is rare though, according to a chair. Refining the grading by dividing those who have received the overall grade 5 (on the scale of 1–7) into sub-groups has in some cases helped to find a joint decision. If a consensus on a final score cannot be reached, the panel can also vote. Regarding this, panel members expressed some hesitation and uncertainty on when and how to use re-ranking, however, as one panel member illustrates:

“But it’s not clear to me then what we can do or should [use re-ranking] and there is, there have been a couple of people on the panel both years who sort of raised this as a question and we don’t really understand ultimately what we are supposed to do, we are supposed to be aware of gender equality in the process and that’s good and everybody is happy with that but ultimately, it hasn’t been a big problem because our results have basically been proportionate.” (A, panel member)

It seems that no clear instructions on re-ranking are provided in the panel briefing session and that explanations about the underlying idea of this policy could be clearer. This reviewer seems to identify some tension between a gender-fair assessment process that then leads to a certain funding outcome and a certain outcome that is fixed while having to prioritise scientific quality.

The situation may not be the same every year though, and some years the quality of applications from either women or men was described by the Chairs to have been better. When asked about how SRC sees deviation of equal success rates, one Chair explained that looking at success rates from year to year has less significance than when comparing success rates of men and women over a multiannual period: *“Yes, they say we can’t look from year-to-year, we have to look over three years maybe [...]” (A, panel chair).*

At FWF, the outcomes need to be gender-balanced in each meeting (there are five panel meetings per year). After all applications have been discussed and graded, the FWF panels need to check if the 50:50 quota was

met. This process is steered by the chair who first informs the panel members about the overall final number of applications that can be granted (on the basis of the available budget). Then the chair checks the number of applications from female applicants which have already been approved (grade A). In the next step, applications from female researchers in the pool of potentially fundable projects (grade A minus) are identified and added to the list of approved projects. If then still fewer women are granted, the lacking number of applications from female researchers needs to be selected from all B1 applications.

Achieving this quota worked differently in the three meetings we observed: In one panel meeting, the number of applications from women and men was equal after the last proposal was discussed, so no further step or discussion was needed. At the end of the second panel meeting, the lacking number of female applicants could be exactly retrieved from the A minus pool, arguing that *“the procedure foresees that we fund exactly those (...) projects”* (B, panel member). In the third panel meeting, the panels really had to negotiate who is selected for funding, but as one of the applicants discussed had not provided IC, the GRANteD research team was unfortunately not able to observe this interesting negotiation.

In the three panels observed, no down-ranking of male applicants nor up-ranking of female applicants was practiced. Rather the final list was not completed, and space was left for selecting the ‘right’ additional applications at the end.

In SFI panels, tie-breaking takes place after all applications have been reviewed. Yet this is not a social process in the panel, but a technical procedure done by the IT system based on the ranking of highest scores. A ranking list of applications is produced, based on overall average scores that are rounded to the nearest 0.5. Within these bands, women are ranked first and then the final list of applications suggested for funding is created. Nothing is discussed in the panels, panel members are not involved in the re-ranking and at the end of the panel meeting, they do not know who was re-ranked and who was recommended for funding.

4.3.4 Support for re-ranking policy

In the FWF panel meetings, re-ranking as a policy was hardly discussed. It was remarkable that the 50 % quota for female FWF applicants was never mentioned or questioned in the panel meetings. It seemed to be a given policy, supported by the chair, and panel members were aware that a sufficient number of women need to be funded to meet the policy target. In the SFI panel negotiations observed, no references to tie-breaking were made.

In contrast to panel members, staff members actively referred to this policy and mostly expressed support: SRC informants stated that the implementation of the policy works out well; chairs, staff members and observers spoke with confidence on re-ranking as a well-established policy. SFI representatives stressed that such a policy is needed and that it aims to correct for an *“error in the system and (...) that women tend to be marked tighter”* (C, staff). Nevertheless, FWF representatives argued after three panel meetings that they felt *“relieved”* that there was no trouble with down-ranking. It seems that they felt somewhat apprehensive about this policy.

While NCN does not have re-ranking policies, panel members who were asked about this policy expressed their concern, as explained by one of the informants: *“I would be quite against setting rules, formal or informal rules, that certain gender parity should be reached”* (NCN, panel member).

5 DISCUSSION

Studying work in panels (also called boards, expert teams or councils) qualitatively enabled us to understand what is going on in panels, how and when gender is or is not addressed and how this relates to gender bias. Having gained more detailed insights into the practices of panel work we now move on to discuss some of the challenges raised in the interviews or identified in the panel observations in a broader perspective, and consider ways of making research assessment and decision-making more (gender-)fair.

Gender relations are relevant on two levels: Gender plays a role directly when we analyse how gender is explicitly addressed in panel meetings and how formal policies already implemented to foster gender fairness work in practice. When looking at the assessment process, we also analyse how guidelines for reviewing and decision-making in general are applied in practice and what potential risks can be identified in respect to gender fairness. To optimise these procedures for more fairness and transparency in general means, at the same time, increasing the fairness for female applicants. The same holds for other underrepresented groups that may also have less access to inside information on the funding process and less support due to homosocial or marginalising networking patterns.

5.1 Various and changing roles of panels

Panels are not panels – they differ between RFOs in various aspects – this was one clear finding when we studied assessment practices in five RFOs in depth. The findings thus show, how review panels in RFOs differ in respect to the role they have within the whole assessment process including decision-making. These differences matter when discussing risks for gender bias in practice, as discussed in the following.

5.1.1 Function of panels

First, panels differ and change in respect to their function within the assessment process. We need to be aware that RFOs have very different assessment procedures in place. Some panels assess proposals (rating, or rating and ranking), other panels assess the quality of remote review(er)s, and also intermediate forms exist. We also learned that some RFOs are continuously (slightly) adopting the role of their panels in order to improve the assessment process. However, despite the intention to improve the assessment process, this restructuring could also lead to challenges and risks for a (gender-)fair implementation. In the FFP2020 call, SFI has implemented the so-called Oversight Sitting Panels, which assess the quality of remote reviews only, but are not supposed to discuss the proposal, PI and excellence, respectively. When studying how this was implemented in practice, we found some confusions about what can be brought up in panels. Panel members were not clear on how to assess the quality and fairness of remote reviewers and some panel members stuck to their ‘old’ function and discussed their own assessment of the applicant’s quality and excellence. Accordingly, it happened that gendered assessment aspects like the number of publications in respect to academic age or maternity leave were raised, although gender is not supposed to be an issue in

the new SFI panel format. Ideally, these panels do not assess applicants, which might overall contribute to a lower accountability of panel members for gender fairness.

In SFI, the remote reviewers are now the ones who are assessing excellence and are supposed to apply newly implemented formal policies – such as the ‘holistic’ concept of excellence or the gender dimension in research – in their practice. Our interviews with remote reviewers indicate that committing them to implementing new policies is challenging, as the remote reviewers never get in personal contact with the RFO, neither online nor on-site. This challenge also holds for other RFOs (FWF, NCN, SRDA), which involve remote reviewers in the assessment process. Remote reviewers work individually, they have no chance to learn from each other or to share experiences, calibrate their views against other reviewers, and get used to new standards as panel members do. As a result of this the NCN panels were for example sometimes hesitant to include the assessments from some of the remote reviewers in their final rating and ranking of the proposals, as they diverged too much from what the panel had agreed upon during the first meeting. Or the SRDA panels took the opportunity to change the average score of applications, when not agreeing with one or both of the assessments of the remote reviewers. SFI panels revised the scores of remote reviewers. Here, when remote reviewers’ scores and written assessments are controlled for their quality by panel members, it would be crucial that this assessment is fed back to them. This way remote reviewers can learn and get used to apply the standards the RFO aims to apply, for instance on how to assess the gender-in-research dimension, how to assess a narrative CV or how to do the assessment without the h-index.

Especially, if remote reviewers have greater decision-making power and panels serve more as control bodies for them (as it is the case with the panels of the FFP funding programme), RFOs should place a greater focus on remote reviewers and their assessment work regarding discussions and analysis of gender bias.

5.1.2 Final decision making in panels

Second, panels differ in respect to their role in the final funding decision. Some decide who gets funded (FWF), while others are advisory bodies which only make a funding suggestion (SFI, SRC, NCN, SRDA) that is later confirmed or rejected by another legal body (board or council) higher up in the hierarchy. In some panels the members do not know who gets funded at the end of the assessment process, e.g. the SFI final suggested ranking list is produced by the IT system, after an algorithm-based re-ranking had taken place.

5.1.3 Internationalisation of panels

Panels also differ in respect to the internationalisation of their members. While some are only (FWF) or mainly (SRDA, SRC) composed of researchers working in the country where the RFO is located, others consist mainly (NCN) or fully (SFI) of researchers working abroad. NCN reformed their expert teams (i.e. panels) about five years ago, switching from including primarily national members to instead using international reviewers. The main motivation for this shift from national to international panel members was to increase fairness in the review process and decrease the risk of corruption and bias. SRDA has just started a similar process of changing the panel composition. The proximity to the national scientific community influences the practice of panel work in various manners and entails both challenges and benefits: On the one hand, nationally dominated panels need strict COI regulations and need to frequently

and consequently apply them to avoid nepotism. On the other hand, a higher share of international experts means that panel members have different cultural backgrounds and are not necessarily familiar with the career system of the RFO country. They might, however, introduce more openness and heterogeneous experiences from other research funding organisations on how to deal with specific challenges, for example on how to attract more female applicants in STEM fields. Aiming for a more inclusive scientific community and a more diverse group of grantees, it could also be beneficial to attract an even broader range of reviewers, including more researchers with migration background, from countries of the Global South, as well as younger researchers or people from non-academic research organisations. It has been pointed out in our fieldwork that international panel members are often not aware of the national scientific context and thus are not clear about what can be expected from applicants. It is then up to the RFO to instruct them and clarify national standards. This was for example a matter emphasized in the NCN panels, where the inclusion of some Polish scientists was described as important for sharing national specific information. The active role the NCN coordinators and administrators take during panel meetings was also described as important for increasing the understanding of the Polish context among the international panel members. The Polish panel members and chairs interviewed also shared that they took it upon themselves to explain for example the situation for women and mothers in Poland.

Overall, one main contribution from the GRANteD case studies in WP 6 is that they highlight differences between panels in different RFOs and how these differences may or may not foster gender equality in the work of panels.

5.2 Excellence (scientific quality, merits)

The case studies give information about the challenges that panels in different RFOs face when assessing excellence. We got insights into the way formal assessment criteria are applied and measured in practice; further it was shown whether and how panels deal with innovative elements of excellence. Excellence is difficult to capture and refers to reviewers' individual standards, as has been demonstrated by a broad body of research (for example O'Connor and O'Hagan 2020, Schiffbänker et al. 2022). RFOs play a crucial role in making transparent what excellence in their respective setting means. By defining formal excellence criteria and by defining how excellence is *measured*, RFOs define what excellence is: "*Excellence is what is funded as excellence*" (EC 2022). RFOs need to make clear what applicants are expected to report and what reviewers are expected to assess.

Even when excellence criteria are formalised, however, these standards are not necessarily applied in practice in a systematic manner. Panel members and RFOs face various challenges when they assess scientific excellence, as identified in our fieldwork and discussed in the next sections.

5.2.1 Applying criteria

When observing panels, we found evidence that one challenge in panels is to apply the same criteria to each application: Not all formal criteria are necessarily applied in panels, some criteria were only mentioned once or a very few times and played no role in the assessment of all other applications. This also holds for negative criteria: Our observations indicated, for example, that not having an ERC grant was pointed out for one (female) applicant, while this standard was not applied to any other applicant discussed in this

panel. Furthermore, other panel members brought in specific criteria they might personally perceive as relevant for assessing excellence, for example, it was argued that applicants are excellent as they were very active in research-related activities like science communication and review work, although their publication output was discussed as not so impressive. When different excellence criteria are brought in for different applicants, not all applicants are assessed against the same criteria and standards.

We may conclude that to guarantee (gender) fairness, accountability is needed in applying the same standards to all applications, making the panel chair or observers (from the RFO or external) responsible for this in panel meetings and obliging the RFO to provide some support structures.

5.2.2 Adopting criteria – ‘new’ excellence

All RFOs in our study are part of the European Research Area, in which gender equality is an important goal. Some RFOs have started revising some assessment criteria to align them with standards defined by the European Commission. It could be observed that national funders increasingly ask applicants to integrate a gender approach in their research design, research questions and analysis. This means that remote reviewers and / or panel members are asked to assess how gender is addressed to increase research excellence. Now reviewers from various fields have to assess if the gender dimension was integrated in the research proposal sufficiently – which requires some understanding and knowledge on gender. In our fieldwork it became evident that most panel members and remote reviewers did not understand this policy and mostly link it to the representation of women in research teams. This shows that panel members and remote reviewers need a better understanding of how gender is inscribed in various research topics and how gender aspects contribute to more excellent research. Panel members and remote reviewers also need more gender awareness to be able to recognise and assess gender relevance in the applications they read. Building these capacities is suggested for remote reviewers (as well as for panel members). Some RFOs, such as SRC, are providing guidance on integrating the sex and gender dimension in research on their websites, and there are international resources for this purpose, which could be made more known to RFOs, such as the Gendered Innovations Portal and the GenPORT portal.

Another context in which RFOs start revising excellence criteria are ongoing international efforts and declarations concerning the reform of the research assessment, like DORA, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment which was signed by over 100 RFOs worldwide and strives for “*changes in assessment practices for research, researchers and research organisations*” and, more specifically, encourages them to “*review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes*” (EC 2022, 9). These initiatives aim to change the research culture, to foster a broader concept of excellence and to adapt assessment criteria and procedures accordingly.

Three of our five case study RFOs (SFI, FWF and NCN) signed the DORA declaration, although its implementation in practice differs. In our fieldwork, we have seen that some RFOs have started adopting formal assessment procedures and assessment practices. They have suggested avoiding a focus on publication numbers and the use of the h-index. These formal adoptions have been implemented only recently. SFI has implemented a new template to report research merits qualitatively (= narrative CV) and in a broader perspective. However, remote reviewers who assessed the newly implemented criteria provided ambivalent feedback about this new instrument: While some see the narrative CV as chance ‘to

change the rules' in the science system, others argue that careers are built on publications and thus publications need to be the core of each PI's assessment. Further, without using the h-index, some informants argued that reviewers lack references and do not always trust the information that applicants report (see 5.2.3). In general, the interviews with panel members/remote reviewers of all three RFOs, which signed DORA (FWF, NCN and SFI) revealed, even when informed about new standards, it takes time, but also practice to become used to them. For many panel members and remote reviewers, it requires a 'change of mind-set', as it was argued by informants from NCN and SFI. In case of NCN, only a handful of the panel members interviewed in NCN were familiar with or mentioned DORA as important.

Further challenges emerge when RFOs introduced new standards for excellence, like broadening the set of criteria (SFI) or talking about an applicant's merits and quality instead of excellence (SRC). Furthermore, that applicants have to include a mentor and report about mentoring activities in their application (FWF, SFI) can be seen as an innovative element reimagining the idea of an excellent junior researcher; they need to be reflected in assessment criteria as well.

To align ongoing developments for advancing assessment standards it could be an idea to establish an international forum where RFOs and further stakeholders (e.g. RFO umbrella organisations, CoARA) reflect and share their mutual experiences. This forum could be established as prestigious meeting (as it is the World Economic Forum for business leaders), organised every year or every second year and providing recommendations how to enhance standards that take gender and intersectional aspects (see 5.6) into account.

Panel members and remote reviewers should also be aware that a more qualitative reporting and, even more, assessing of qualitative information might open doors for new potential gender bias factors. It was mentioned by some informants that women might have a different style for presenting their merits. Thus, reviewers need some reflexivity and awareness to avoid that male standards are established as norm. RFOs should critically observe this and intervene immediately. Similar to SRC, external observers could be invited to reveal biased practices and enable learning. Raising awareness on potential pitfalls could help to avoid disappointment for reviewers, RFOs as well as applicants.

5.2.3 *Measuring 'new' excellence*

As long as publications, citations and impact points are the core of excellence, the h-index and further metrics matter. Panel members have raised concerns about the h-index as it does not consider career breaks or other leaves, which might disfavour especially women. Problems also emerge in interdisciplinary panels with different disciplinary publication and citation patterns: Here, panel members might assess the h-index of an applicant in another field based on an average h-index in their own discipline. Nevertheless, the h-index was also highlighted, for example in the NCN and SRDA panels, as an efficient instrument to assess the scientific output quickly. Panel members and remote reviewers see this as particular relevant in fields outside their own expertise. Panel members argued that this reference is needed to be able to trust an applicant's information and reported that they look up the h-index in Scopus or Google Scholar to assess whether the applicant's information is true (even if they were asked by the respective RFO not to do so, e.g. NCN and SFI). Here, a challenge emerges for RFOs: Remote reviewers and panel members asked for guidance on how to assess qualitative track records. Also enabling them to exchange experiences and build

capacities on how to deal with the new standards (GiRI, no h-index) might be beneficial, especially for remote reviewers who work in isolation compared to panel members (see already 5.1.1). It was argued that remote reviewers might need more time to do the assessment properly without relying on the h-index, so different forms of compensation could be introduced (financial, or more time for reviewing). Otherwise, remote reviewers with very limited time resources – in particular, female reviewers with an already high workload – could be discouraged to do review work.

5.3 Gender balancing funding outcomes: re-ranking policies

Some RFOs are striving for gender equality by aiming for equal success chances of female and male applicants. Comparing success rates of female and male applicants has been a starting point for discussing gender bias in the allocation of research grants. Success rates shift the focus to the funding outcomes and differences there. While research and RFO policies have increasingly worked to eradicate bias in the research assessment process, RFOs have also implemented policies that explicitly strive for (more) gender-balanced funding outcomes. In chapters 4.3.2 to 4.3.4 we described different policies that aim to ensure that funding outcomes are gender-balanced, how they are practiced and supported.

To achieve this, proposals are re-ranked, aiming for a defined distribution of male and female grantees, either the same number of grantees per gender or the same share of successful applicants per gender (equal success rates). The overall RFO aim is to make sure that a sufficient number of women is granted.

We have seen different policies in place to achieve this goal: SFI uses a form of automatic, IT-based re-ranking, panel members playing no direct role in implementing this policy. Based on the final average score, proposals are ranked within 0.5 bands and within these bands preference is given to female applicants in order to have more female grantees. In the FWF ESPRIT programme, proposals are re-ranked by panel members at the end of each panel meeting in order to have the same number of male and female grantees. As the share of female applicants is lower, this quota can be seen as kind of affirmative action. In the SRC case, re-ranking is used as a borderline condition, in case of applications evaluated to be of the same scientific quality, the underrepresented sex can be prioritised to improve gender balance of grantees, but this is not an automatic procedure.

RFO staff representatives pointed out various arguments why re-ranking policies contribute to gender fairness in the assessment of research grants. A main argument was that as female and male applicants are equal in terms of excellence or quality, success rates (over a defined period) need to be equal as well. Other RFO staff members argued that the assessment process is not biased (and some RFOs have done research on this in their RFO) and thus female applicants should be equally successful as male applicants. This was also argued the other way round: RFO staff representatives stated that research has clearly demonstrated various bias factors in the assessment process (assessing the same quality differently for different applicants, applying different standards to male and female applicants, not considering that some applicants have less time to produce the expected outcome, etc.) and to compensate for this female applicants as a group need to be prioritised in a formalised manner.

A guaranteed number of female grantees was seen as a signal and incentive to encourage female researchers to apply and thus increase the number of female applicants. In the Austrian context, the quota

that guarantees an equal number of female grantees was seen as a requirement to avoid a decreasing number of women applying after two women-only-funding programmes had been discontinued by the FWF.

Having in mind the intended number of female grantees might further reinforce the relevance of (discussing) sex/gender within these panels (while other RFOs strive for 'de-gendering' applicants, see 5.5.1). The focus is on the representation of women. We have learned that when panels strive for an absolute number of women to be granted, in order to meet this number, more women might be selected from female-dominated fields, so that a low number of women grantees in one field (Technical Sciences) could be compensated for by a high number of women grantees in another field (e.g. Life Sciences) in order to make the overall goal. This way a fixed number of female grantees might, in fact, reinforce already existing gender segregation in science.

When studying the implementation of these policies in practice we learned that the focus on numbers, on a gender-balanced *outcome* might limit the focus on the *process*. Having in mind the number of women to be funded might limit attention to and awareness of gender in all other aspects of the panel meeting, like gender-neutral language, the role of care responsibilities in respect to publications, the fact that excellence criteria can be gendered or the way the gender dimension was integrated in the content of research proposals discussed. With this kind of focus, the gender awareness of RFO staff, RFO management, remote reviewers or panel/board members is also not addressed.

For FWF panels, it can be stated more generally that the focus on numbers at the end of the assessment process (= the focus on outcomes of the assessment process) limited the focus on the process and its gendered nature. As at the end of the board meeting, gender had to be addressed anyway by checking for the 50 % female grantees, less awareness was needed on gendered aspects in the process before. To put it more bluntly: Any gender bias would be corrected with the 50 % gender-equal approval rate anyway, thus the formal gender goal would be met, irrespective of what has happened before. This should not be understood in a way that panel members ignored any gender rules consciously, but they did not need to pay too much attention to them. This way, re-ranking policies bear the risk to reduce gender to counting heads and to the representation of women grantees.

More generally, a focus on gender-equal approval rates has the potential risk to narrow down the understanding of gender merely to the number of women grantees, so to the representation of women. Taking gender into account in the assessment process is not really relevant as the outcome at the end is corrected anyway. Here, we should be aware, from a gender fairness perspective, that the selection of applicants who have made it to the ranking list – which serves as basis for the re-ranking – could be done with limited gender awareness and gender fairness and thus would be gender-biased. One of the main conclusions is that focusing only on gender-balanced outcomes cannot balance out a gender-insensitive assessment process.

A further insight was that panel members do not necessarily understand the purpose of a re-ranking policy. RFOs are encouraged to inform the involved actors about the underlying argumentation for implementing this policy. When re-ranking policies are applied, we need to be aware of tensions between the aim to bring in more female applicants and have equal success rates and the aim to apply the same criteria for all. In

contrast, re-ranking should compensate for potential bias in the assessment process or even before the assessment process, in the applicants' careers.

5.4 Putting formal policies into practice

Another finding refers to the implementation of the formal policies already in place (to mitigate gender bias). When studying the level of gender awareness in institutions, we usually look at the formal policies and regulations in place. Formal policies are indeed a crucial lever for institutions to foster change. So, for analysing gender bias in the funding process, monitoring and comparing formal policies to mitigate gender bias (for instance Husu and De Cheveigné 2010) are important steps. For our five RFOs case studies, the formal organisational and national policies have been analysed in detail in GRANteD deliverable 5.1. (Husu and Peterson 2022).

To learn about the effectiveness of formal policies we need to know whether and how they are in fact implemented and applied in practice. Research on policy implementation underlines the complexities of implementation. Carey et al. (2019) argue that *“while implementation is often portrayed as a simple process of adopting best practice, experiences indicate that it is a far more complex process involving a range of actors translating policy into practice under varying conditions.”*

In our fieldwork we found that formal assessment policies are not necessarily applied in practice. More precisely, panellists and reviewers only partially apply the general and gender equality policies of the RFO in place for assessing applications. The challenge to bring policies into practice, the need for more reflexivity and awareness on policies, has been raised by emerging as well as by advanced RFOs - as panel members and remote reviewers who care less of formal policies can be found in all RFOs. This challenge concerns gender equality policies as well as general aspects of the research assessment. To mitigate bias, the RFO might have a strong interest in changing this behaviour. Understanding the reasons can be a step to change. Additionally, we bring in some ideas that support the implementation of formal policies in practice.

5.4.1 Resistances

One reason for not applying formal policies of the RFO in practice might be that policies exist, but are not known by the panel members and remote reviewers. Another possibility might be that policies are not noted or they are known, but panel members and remote reviewers do not look into them in detail, because they assume that they know what they are about. Staff members of RFOs with more advanced gender equality policies confirmed that different gender equality policies are in place: e.g., gender awareness trainings (often online to be more convenient for international panel members and remote reviewers); briefing sessions at the beginning of panel meetings to inform about the procedures of the meeting and (new) policies in place; written guidelines and information to inform panel members/remote reviewers about assessment details (e.g. how to assess the gender in research dimension).

So one can conclude that RFOs with more extensive gender equality policies and measures in place try to inform their panel members and remote reviewers about these policies and measures in the best way. It seems that the information does not reach the recipient in the way it should as panel members and remote reviewers do not make use of it. The interviews provide clues in this respect. Especially international panel members and remote reviewers are often active in various RFOs in different countries. In the interviews it

became obvious that these panel members and remote reviewers quite easily mix-up policies, especially if they are quite similar across RFOs, for which panel members and remote reviewers work. In the interviews with for example NCN panel members or SFI remote reviewers some of them referred to policies that are not implemented in the respective RFO. In NCN, where the panels evaluated applications to different funding instruments during the same meeting, the problem with mixing-up policies and guidelines for reviewing the different grants (e.g. pre-doctoral grants, early-career grants or advanced grants) was further enhanced. The interviews revealed that due to their various obligations, time of panel members and remote reviewers is very limited and they do not read all instructions they receive from each RFO. So it easily could happen that gender equality guidelines are not checked in detail or at all.

Another reason for not applying policies and measures might be a certain resistance against instructions of RFOs. Some panel members and remote reviewers expressed that their scientific competences and experiences are undermined by such instructions. Some argued that they are experienced researchers, and also experienced evaluators as reviewing scientific work is a core element of their professional life, reviewing constantly students' work and applications in national and international RFOs. This way they develop their 'individual understanding' of how to practice reviewing, what to look at and what to take into account. Here the questions arise to what extent reviewers are willing to become well informed or 'educated' and how existing and/or new policies can be designed so that they have an impact on the behaviour of reviewers and panels. These findings are in line with feminist implementation theory (e.g. Carey et al. 2019, Van den Brink 2021) which has argued that implementation in practice is not trivial but a complex process and one that faces various challenges.

5.4.2 *Facilitators*

When thinking about measures to support that formal policies are better applied in practice, one idea is to optimise the format of existing support material (guidelines, trainings). Exploring appropriate formats for informing panel members (and also remote reviewers) in a sustainable manner and building capacities is a main challenge for RFOs. RFO staff members suggested multiple formats and channels as they have observed that panel members have different preferences: Some prefer that updates are provided in short briefing sessions just at the beginning of a panel meeting, others prefer online training they can take part in at any time (e.g. when travelling to a panel meeting).

Distinguishing between more general policies that need to be applied in practice and innovative approaches – which ask reviewers to adopt new (ground-breaking) ways of thinking, like giving up the h-index – can be helpful for finding the right format. Our data indicates that for complex issues, only informing about the policy might not be sufficient, but some more substantial ways of providing background knowledge or enabling in-depth learning and anchoring might be needed, for example, when fostering a different concept of excellence. To meet the demands of the different reviewers involved, offering a mix of methods seems effective. Generally, it can be said, that formats that physically take place and requires the active involvement of panel members and/or remote reviewers are probably the most effective ones. Those of course are, however, costly in every respect (time, personal, infrastructural, ecological resources). Therefore, one option could be to test and promote (more) online formats, especially to bring (international) remote reviewers on the same page and also to align reviewing standards. In particular for GiRI and for how to assess a narrative CV online formats might be good option to inform more

comprehensively. Also, although keeping the time is a critical issue during the panel meetings, the importance of having a brief but comprehensive introduction to the evaluation process and a repetition of the most central guidelines at the start of the meeting was emphasized by both panel members and chairs in for example NCN and SRC.

RFO representatives expressed some understanding for that it takes time until (new) policies are accepted and applied. However, RFOs should make sure that reviewers are aware of these new standards and focus on them in their evaluation process. Otherwise, those applicants who are adopting new standards – like GiRI - would be penalised. New standards require appropriate knowledge among all panel members. It takes time, but also practice, to become used to new standards that, require a ‘change of mindset’, as argued by informants from NCN and SFI.

Furthermore, our fieldwork revealed that reviewers – both remote reviewers and panel members – often do not understand why a policy was implemented and what the underlying ideas and concepts are (e.g. why the integration of gender in research content is needed). This makes it more difficult and less motivating to apply them appropriately. Providing more information and raising awareness about the underlying narratives of a policy and what it aims for could make it easier to put these policies into practice. The RFO websites, magazines, annual reports and other communication activities could be useful here. And more generally, informing reviewers again and again about the gender targets could contribute to keeping up a certain level of gender awareness and thus support applying formal gender policies in practice.

Finally, also RFO internal processes and practices influence how effective formal policies might be implemented in practice. RFOs might think about strengthening the accountability for the implementation of policies in practice, for example, by making the chair (more clearly) responsible or having specific observers who can interfere or interrupt panel negotiations in case a formal policy is not applied. Trainings for chairs are a crucial step to make them aware of the standards and to enable them to anchor the RFO standards in panel work. An example of this was when SFI implemented a different function for their FFP2020 panels, and SFI scientific officers actively interrupted panel members who did not stick to the newly implemented rule.

5.5 Building capacity and steering inclusion

A final important issue is how RFOs can actively support the implementation of general assessment policies and gender equality policies in practice, and in which way they can optimise the awareness and knowledge of involved actors and processes, and formats to promote this. This follows the overall aim to contribute to a more inclusive research environment, aiming for research to benefit all and to include diverse actors: *“Without widespread awareness (...) and training of those assessed and, crucially, assessors, progress will be slow – if not impossible”* (EC 2021, 9).

Our fieldwork has shown that applying formal RFO policies in practice does not only require awareness, but also skills, competences and knowledge. When RFOs adjust their policies or implement new ones, evaluators are requested to rethink their current concepts and to adjust their (assessment) behaviour accordingly. RFOs should encourage evaluators in that and provide support in the best way.

Based on our empirical findings reported in the previous chapters, we now discuss capacity-building in respect to requested content, relevant target groups and appropriate (innovative) formats.

5.5.1 *Gender awareness, gender competence – or no/more gender?*

RFOs have implemented various policies to increase gender fairness. To be able to apply these policies, the relevant actors need capacities about gender. In practice, however, many reviewers appear to *lack awareness* of why these policies are relevant (see already 5.4.2). Lack of awareness concerns/covers how and where gender is relevant in the assessment process, the potential risks for bias and the policies aiming to mitigate these risks. Lacking gender awareness makes it difficult to apply the formal gender policies implemented by RFOs in the manner they aim to, and new policies in respect to (gender) fairness cannot be fully implemented. Research argues that in general, RFO (management and staff), remote reviewers and panel members should increase their understanding of the ways in which R&I projects can be gendered (Pecis 2016). Also, among the ten principles defined by the EC to reform the research assessment system (EC 2021), gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness are explicitly mentioned. Indeed, some RFO members argued that gender competence should become a quality standard and *“reviewers should not be selected anymore in case they are not gender-sensitive”*. But it was also stated that time is needed to develop this gender-sensitiveness, while knowing that *“reviewers are scientists and scientists are used to integrate findings in their thinking”* (C, remote reviewer).

No/more gender?

One specific question in respect to gender emerged in various RFOs: How much weight should gender in the panel work carry? In this regard, there are different arguments: Panel members with limited gender awareness argued that gender is not relevant, as it is excellence that counts. Panel members from RFOs with long traditions in gender equality measures also argue that gender does not play a role *anymore*: As people are aware of any gender pitfalls, and bias factors and policies are in place to mitigate them, gender can ‘disappear’. Reviewers sometimes feel some gender fatigue; for others distinguishing between women and men seems inappropriate. Some RFOs request panel members to ‘ignore’ gender by talking in a gender-neutral way and not to mention the gender of an applicant or a name, only the proposal ID; this is supposed to create an objective atmosphere and to avoid activating gender stereotypes. Not paying attention to gender and making it invisible is seen as an approach for gender fairness.

At the same time, RFOs have gender targets in place, for instance re-ranking policies that aim for a pre-defined number of female grantees – which shifts the attention strongly to the applicant’s gender. Some panel members argued for a ‘gender earmarking’ to know better which applications were submitted by women. Making gender visible then is seen as an approach for gender fairness.

5.5.2 *GiRI capacities*

As discussed above, some RFOs now ask applicants to incorporate the sex and gender dimension into research and innovation content, following EC requirements. When studying how this is assessed by remote reviewers and panel members, we found a lack of clarity and understanding for the concept. Gender in research content and gender balance in research teams were mixed up. Moreover, most reviewers do not

understand the aim of this policy and how GiRI contributes to better research and more scientific excellence.

When reviewers assess GiRI, however, they need to understand the concept and, beyond that, they need specific competence for assessing GiRI, fine-tuned for their research field. Based on their own (lacking) gender awareness, remote reviewers might not be able to assess the gender relevance in a proposal or reject the applicant's argument that gender plays no role in this area. Our data confirm that reviewers sometimes did not see any gender relevance or argued that gender is not the focus of the project. Recognising the relevance of gender in the very specific research fields – for example, climate change – requires awareness about how sex/gender impacts the generation of knowledge and innovation. It is obvious that remote reviewers need capacities to assess whether and how GiRI was implemented in the various proposals, not confusing it with the representation of women.

Asked about guidance for how to apply GiRI, remote reviewers confirmed that support material and training are offered by the RFO. Nevertheless, this support material did not bring clarity for how to apply GiRI in practice. It became evident, therefore, that reviewers need more awareness and a better understanding about why to take GiRI into account and how the quality and excellence of research and innovation can benefit. Hunt et al. (2022) argued that funders need to ask reviewers *“to provide a rationale for their rating along with recommendations to applicants for improvement”*. What is needed is better guidance and more efforts to enhance knowledge that enables reviewers to identify gender relevance.

For building these capacities, formats provided so far are guidance, guidelines, trainings, personal coaching, open access software and best practices structured by thematic fields or an expert pool of gender scholars for collaboration. Further knowledge on GiRI is currently developed by EU-funded projects like INSPIRE or GENDERACTIONplus.

The most effective format – given the time constraints of remote reviewers and panel members – is not clear yet. Our data suggest that it is not only about 'learning' how to do it, but more about gradually developing these competences, which is why RFOs could support reviewers by offering platforms or networks to share experiences and knowledge when assessing GiRI. Communities of Practice could be established. These measures can also be offered on a broader institutional level, for example, by umbrella organisations like Science Europe, other knowledge providers or different funding agencies together, for example on a regional basis; this might increase their impact.

But not only panel members and remote reviewers, also researchers need more capacities to apply GiRI. By making 'gender in research' training for researchers an eligible programme cost (O'Connor 2022), RFOs can take a main step to encourage them to develop capacities for integrating sex and gender in their research design and analysis. As early as in the proposal development, opportunities could be provided for researchers to discuss their specific research approach with gender scholars. For this, labs or research groups could be initiated and funded that provide the opportunity to fine-tune research ideas and to establish networks for future research projects. Furthermore, capacity-building can be stimulated by specific funding schemes bringing researchers from different scientific fields into contact with gender

scholars to develop topic-specific gender-related research questions and projects (see Austrian funding scheme ‘FEMtech Research Projects’¹⁷).

Finally, RFOs need to think about how to extend GiRI to a more inclusive, intersectional approach which goes beyond gender and takes needs of various societal groups into account, following Bhatia et al. (2022): *“There is a need to move from quantitative gender equality to qualitative inclusivity to enable an inclusive research content”*.

5.5.3 Organising virtual panels

Capacities are also needed in respect to the best format of panel meetings. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the panels we studied met virtually. This enabled us to get insights into how panels work virtually and how panel members reflect on their online experiences. For organising and designing peer review panels in post-pandemic times, this information can be beneficial.

When observing virtual panels, we noticed that negotiations are quite structured, in line with Ufoft et al. (2021), who argue that video-mediated participant observations show *“a lack of mess”* and that online observations are more *“sterilised”*, as participants followed the formal agenda and no informal interactions took place. That panel negotiations were not lively was another observation, providing evidence that in computer-mediated communication *“working through electronic means creates process losses. These are due to lower social presence, fewer social cues in the communication (i.e., the medium is leaner) (...) and less inhibited communications contributing to conflict and misunderstandings”* (Ortiz de Guinea et al 2005, 18). Further research on this would be needed.

So far, our empirical data do not allow us to systematically identify the chances and limitations of the online format in contrast to on-site panels, as we could only observe one on-site panel. From interviewing panel members, however, we learned about their perceptions, partly by comparing them to previous panel meetings that were held online (Peterson and Husu 2022).

Some RFOs have argued that they will continue organising panels online, stating that these are cheaper for the RFO as no travel costs need to be covered, they have a better ecological footprint and might be more inclusive as they enable researchers who are faced with travel restrictions, due to care obligations, disabilities or ecological reasons, to participate. This can be a relevant argument for including more women and enlarging the pool of peer reviewers and panel members by including more scientists from other continents.

5.6 Intersectionality, inclusion

Recent policy discussions and research development regarding equality and fairness in Europe and beyond have moved towards addressing further inequalities in addition to gender, as focusing only on gender does not capture all forms of exclusion and biases in science. Further relevant categories are age, ethnic background, socio-economic status, native language or host institution, disability; these dimensions also often intersect, creating multiple marginalisations. An intersectional approach takes these overlapping

¹⁷ See <https://www.ffg.at/femtech-forschungsprojekte>

dimensions into account and enables us to better understand structural barriers and the needs of different subgroups. For this, more differentiated data is needed. So far, most RFOs only distinguish between female and male candidates, collecting only binary gender data – an approach which could be developed further in the near future, considering the range of gender identities. Intersectional data on ethnicity and cultural background is not always simple to collect due to legal constraints related to data privacy. But more diversified data is needed to be able to design and implement effective and targeted policies. In particular, a better integration of intersectionality in the research content – extending the concept of GiRI – asks for further indicators.

Intersectionality is only emerging slowly at the level of RFO policies. Some RFOs started integrating it in their strategic documents, yet intersecting dimensions also need to be reflected in communication in language and pictures. For attracting a broader range of (potential) applicants from other than native cultural backgrounds, from other universities than the main grant-holders, it might be supportive to address them specifically and to make clear that contributions from very different researchers are appreciated.

In panel work, intersectionality as a concept has not arrived yet. Gender intersecting with other dimensions was rarely addressed and was limited to discussions about extension regulations and publications, reflecting an intersection of gender and age. Further efforts in this direction are needed in the near future, for example well-constructed guidelines for reviewers and panel members.

5.7 Limitation of research

Our research underlines the complexity of factors and processes when analysing gender bias in the allocation of research grants. While the focus in this report has been on gender bias, we acknowledge that besides bias due to gender, many other forms of bias are relevant. We have seen in our data references both to further characteristics of applicants (ethnicity, institutional position, native language, age) and RFO context factors (geographic location of the institution, type of the institution represented by the applicant). The importance of these characteristics and factors emerged from our rich qualitative data. However, despite some of these dimensions being addressed occasionally in our data, they could not be studied systematically as they were outside of the scope of the original purpose of the study. Notwithstanding, the multi-level analysis in GRANteD WP 4 and 9 might create more insights.

While these qualitative case studies in five RFOs have provided valuable insights into the work of panels and different panel functions, how panels apply assessment and gender equality policies and panel members' sense-making (Steinbauer et al. 2015), more systematic data are needed to be able to generalise findings. Qualitative case studies are not necessarily used to produce results which are statistically representative of a population. We cannot with certainty conclude that we have included a representative sample of panels to observe, and panel members and chairs to interview. As the sampling strategy builds on Informed Consent some self-selection is to be expected. This means that it is possible that the panel members or remote reviewers that gave IC and took part in the project had a special interest in the GRANteD project and were eager to give insights into their work as panellists or remote reviewers to contribute to this research and therefore to help improving the assessment systems of RFOs. It is also possible that they were more positive to the funding processes and panel practices than those who did not provide Informed Consent. There is thus a risk that some critical voices and important aspects and

experiences have not been included in our case studies. The themes and topics included in this report however constituted distinct patterns, appearing throughout our data, which at the same time also was characterized by nuances and diverse accounts.

Furthermore, not only the panel work and panel practices affect assessment outcomes, but also the work of remote reviewers and RFO processes. Future research may put its focus on these components to provide a fuller and more complete picture of the funding processes and practices. Results from this kind of research may also help to improve (gender) fairness in grant allocation.

Finally, other aspects that can be relevant for bias, for instance how funding budget is distributed between female and male dominated scientific disciplines, are not covered by our analysis - as the focus of D6.1 is on practices in peer review panels.

6 REFERENCES

- Bagues, M., Sylos-Labini, M., Zinovyeva, N. (2017) Does the Gender Composition of Scientific Committees Matter? *American Economic Review*, 107 (4): 1207-38. DOI: 10.1257/aer.20151211.
- Bird, S. R. (1996) Welcome to the Men's Club: Homosociality and the Maintenance of Hegemonic Masculinity, *Gender & Society*, 10(2), 120-132.
- Bol, T., Mathijs de Vaan, M., Arnout van de Rijt, A. (2022) Gender-equal funding rates conceal unequal evaluations, *Research Policy*.
- Bradley, J. (1993) Methodological issues and practices in qualitative research. *Library Quarterly*, 63(4), 431-449.
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77-101.
- Carey, G., Dickinson, H., Olney, S. (2019) What can feminist theory offer policy implementation challenges?. *Evidence & Policy*, 15(1), 143-159.
- Carli, L. L., Alawa, L., Lee, Y., Zhao, B., Kim, E. (2016). Stereotypes About Gender and Science: Women ≠ Scientists. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 40(2), 244–260. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361684315622645>.
- Cecchi, D., Cicognani, S., Kulic, N. (2019). Gender Quotas or Girls' Networks? Evidence from an Italian Research Selection. *Work, Employment and Society*, 33(3), 462–482. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950017018813071>.
- Correll, S.J. (2017) Reducing Gender Biases In Modern Workplaces: A Small Wins Approach to Organizational Change', *Gender & Society*, 31/6: 725–750.
- Cruz Castro, L., Sanz Menéndez, L. (2019). Grant Allocation Disparities from a Gender Perspective: Literature Review. Synthesis Report. D1.1 of GRANteD Project. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20350%2FdigitalCSIC%2F10548>. Permanent URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/10261/200024>.
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021) Towards a reform of the research assessment system: scoping report, Publications Office, 2021.
- European Commission (2022) Agreement of Reforming Research Assessment, https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/09/2022_07_19_rra_agreement_final.pdf.
- Fritch R., Ivarsson, S., Persdotter, M., Foley, C. (2022) Advancing the sex and gender dimension in the research and innovation funding process, Report from the FORGEN CoP workshop, <https://www.genderportal.eu/resources/advancing-sex-and-gender-dimension-research-and-innovation-funding-process>
- Furr, R. M., Wagerman, S. A., & Funder, D. C. (2010). Personality as manifest in behavior: Direct behavioral observation using the Revised Riverside Behavioral Q-Sort (RBQ-3.0). In C. R. Agnew, D. E. Carlston, W. G. Graziano, & J. R. Kelly (Eds.), *Then a miracle occurs: Focusing on behavior in social psychological theory and research* (pp. 186–204). Oxford University Press.
- Gendered innovations <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/>
- GenPORT <https://www.genderportal.eu/>

- Heilman, M. (2001) Description and prescription: How gender stereotypes prevent women's ascent up the organizational ladder, *Journal of Social Forces* 57(4):657-674.
- Howlett, M. (2021) Looking at the 'Field' through a Zoom Lens: Methodological Reflections on Conducting Online Research during a Global Pandemic." *Qualitative Research*: 146879412098569. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794120985691>.
- Hunt, L., Nielsen, M., W., Schiebinger, L. (2022) A Framework for Sex, Gender, and Diversity Analysis in Research, *Science*, Vol 377, Issue 6614, pp. 1492-1495, DOI: 10.1126/science.abp9775.
- Husu, L. (2004) Gatekeeping, gender equality and scientific excellence. In European Commission, DG for Research: Gender and Excellence in the Making, Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities, pp. 69-76.
- Husu, L., Peterson, H., with Schiffbänker, H., Hearn, J., Sauer, A., Hock, M., Walker, D. (2022). Synthesis Report on Contextual Factors, Gender Equality Policy Analysis and Gender Bias Risk Analysis. D5.1. of GRANteD project.
- Husu, L., & De Cheveigné, S. (2010) Gender and gatekeeping of excellence in research funding: European perspectives, in B.Riegraf, B.Aulenbacher, E.Kirsch-Auwärter and Ursula Müller (Eds.) *GenderChange in Academia. Re-Mapping Fields of Work, Knowledge, and Politics from a Gender Perspective*. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, pp. 43-59.
- Lincoln, Y.S., Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage Publications.
- Marsh, H. W., Jayasinghe, U. W., Bond, N. W. (2011). Gender differences in peer reviews of grant applications: A substantive-methodological synergy in support of the null hypothesis model. *Journal of Informetrics*, 5(1), 167-180.
- Martin, P. Y., (2006) Practising Gender at Work: Further Thoughts on Reflexivity, in: *Gender, Work and organisation*, 13(3) 254–276.
- Martin, P. Y., (2003) Said and Done" Versus "Saying and Doing". *Gendering Practices, Practicing Gender at Work*, in: *Gender and Society*, 17(3) 342–366.
- Mayring, P. (2000) Qualitative content analysis. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(2). Retrieved July 28, 2008, from <http://217.160.35.246/fqs-texte/2-00/2-00mayring-e.pdf>.
- Merton, R. K. (1973) *The Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Mutz, R., Bornmann, L., Daniel, H. D. (2015). Does Gender Matter in Grant Peer Review?. An Empirical Investigation Using the Example of the Austrian Science Fund, *Zeitschrift für Psychologie*, 220 (2), 121 – 129, <https://doi.org/10.1027/2151-2604/a000103>.
- Nielsen, M.W. (2017) Gender consequences of a national performance-based funding model: New pieces in an old puzzle', *Studies in Higher Education*, 42/6: 1033–1055.
- O'Connor, P. (2022) 2022 Science Foundation Ireland's Gender Strategy 2016-2020: A Critique by Pat O'Connor, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364030337>
- O'Connor, P., López, E. M., O'Hagan, C., et al. (2020) Micro-political Practices in Higher Education: A Challenge to Excellence as a Rationalising Myth?', *Critical Studies in Education*, 61:195–211.
- Ortiz de Guinea, A., Webster, J., Staples, S. (2012). A meta-analysis of the consequences of virtualness on team functioning. *Information & Management* (49), 301-308 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2012.08.003>.

- Martin, P.Y. (2006) 'Practising Gender at Work: Further Thoughts on Reflexivity', *Gender, Work & Organization*, 13/3: 254-276.
- Patton, M.Q. (2002) *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Pecis, L. (2016) Doing and undoing gender in innovation: Femininities and masculinities in innovation processes, *Human Relations* 69(11), DOI: 10.1177/0018726716634445.
- Peterson, H., Husu, L., (2022) Online panel work through a gender lens: implications of digital peer review meetings, *Science and Public Policy*, O 10.1093/scipol/scac075
- Poggio, B. (2006), Editorial: Outline of a Theory of Gender Practices. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 13: 225-233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0432.2006.00305.x>
- Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) (2020) SFI FFP 2020 Guidelines for Stage 1 Pre-Proposal Virtual Panel Reviewers
- Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) (without year): Guidance on SFI Narrative CVs, <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/sfi-policies-and-guidance/narrative-cv-dora/>
- Schiffbaenker, H., Haas, M., Holzinger, F. (2022) The gendered nature of independence in the context of research funding and excellence. *SN Soc Sci* 2, 275 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-022-00563-w>.
- She Figures (2021). About She figures. <https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/shefigures2021/index.html>
- Singh, C., Patil, S., Poonacha, P., Koduganti, M., Sharma, S. (2021): When the "field" moves online: Reflections on virtual data collection during covid-19, *Ecology, Economy and Society* ; 4(2):149-157, 2021.
- Steinbauer, R., Rhew, N., Chen S., (2015) From stories to schemas: A dual systems model of leaders' organisational sensemaking, in: *Journal of Leadership and organisations Studies*, 22, 404–412
- Utoft, E.H., Søndergaard, M.K., Bendtsen, A-K. (2021): A lack of mess? Advice on undertaking video-mediated participant observations, *Journal of Organizational Ethnography*, 2046-6749 DOI 10.1108/JOE-07-2021-0037
- Van den Besselaar, P., Mom, C. (2020): Identifying gender bias and its causes and effects, D2.1. of GRANteD project.
- Van den Brink, M. (2020) "Reinventing the wheel over and over again". *Organizational learning, memory and forgetting in doing diversity work, Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal* Vol. 39 No. 4, 2020 pp. 379-393 DOI 10.1108/EDI-10-2019-0249
- Van den Brink, M., Benschop, Y. (2012) Gender practices in the construction of academic excellence: Sheep with five legs', *Organization*, 19/4: 507-524.
- Vinkenburg, C.R, Ossenkop, C., Schiffbaenker, H., (2021) Selling science: optimizing the research funding evaluation and decision process; *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*, 41(9), 1-14(14); DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EDI-01-2021-0028>

7 ANNEX

7.1 Coding tree

In Table 6, the coding tree with its meta- and sub-level codes for the coding and analysis process is depicted. To ensure clarity and readability, only the general codes are outlined in this table, which could be applied to the coding and analysis process of all RFOs. Depending on the RFO and the specifics of its funding instrument and decision-making process, further specific codes were developed which then captured this information.

Table 6: General coding tree used for the coding and analysis process of interviews with staff, panel members, remote reviewers and of observations

Meta-level code	Sub-code, level 1	Sub-code, level 2	Sub-code, level 3		
Evaluation in practice	Introduction to panel work	by funding organisation			
		by documents			
		by (previous) chairs/members			
		by training			
		other introduction			
		no introduction			
	Decision-making process	Practices preceding panel meetings			
			Panel meeting	Role of panel	
				Role of panel chair	
				Role of panel members	
				Role of staff and observers (if present)	
				Discussion practices	
				Panel dynamics	
				Gender dynamics	
			Funding decision	Responsible body for final funding decision	
				Final decision-making practices	
		Criteria of excellence	Formal criteria & scales		
				Principle Investigator & research team	
				Scientific excellence of research project	
				GIRI (if in place)	
Gender equality and scientific excellence					
Impact of Covid on decision making process					
	in science				
Understanding Gender					

	in academia		
	in society		
Gender equality policies	Gender equality aims of RFO		
	Gender equality policies in place		
	Gender equality policies/measures that inspired interviewee		
Improving the funding process generally	General measures		
	Gender equality measures		

Source: Own table

7.2 Variables on panels, policies and practices

From the empirical work on policies and practices, variables were developed to be integrated in the work of WP 4 and WP 9. For all variables listed in Table 7, data for all five case study RFOs are provided to be analysed by GRANteD partners.

This data is structured on different levels and variables with their dimensions are depicted (see Table 7):

- The first block of variables refers to the description of the entity (variables on the entity; variables from V 1 to V 5).
- The second block of variables (variables targeting the RFO level; variables from V 6 to V 23) are linked to WP 5 and concern overall policies and measures for the whole RFO. The reference date is 31 December 2020. Measures implemented after this date are not taken into account. These variables therefore hold for each panel of the respective funding programme under consideration.
- The third block of variables (variables targeting the panel level of the funding programme under consideration; variables V 24 to V 60) is linked to WP 6 and to the data generated from the interviews with staff members and panellists or from observations. The data for these variables may differ between different panels of the same funding programme. The reference date when collecting the data also varies between the different RFOs as calls of different years of the different funding programmes were investigated. The reference dates for the different funding programmes are the following:
 - ESPRIT, FWF (AT): 11/2021–05/2022
 - SONATA, NCN (PL): 12/2022
 - Frontiers for Future Programme, SFI (IE): 06/2021
 - International postdoc grant, SRC (SE): 05/2021
 - General Call, SRDA (SK): 06/2021

Table 7: Variables from the qualitative data for WP 4 and WP 9

Variable shortcut	Variable name	Dimensions	Additional explanation
Variables on the entity			
V1	Name of panel	Text	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824574.

V2	Acronym of funding instrument	Text	
V3	Year of call	Numeric variable	
V4	Acronym of RFO	Text	
V5	Country code of the RFO	Text	
Variables targeting the RFO level			
V6	Years since first GE activities were implemented (approximately)	1 = last 1–2 years 2 = approximately the last 5 years 3 = approximately the last 10 years 4 = approximately the last 15 years 5 = approximately the last 20 or more years 6 = Do not know	This concerns the first actions, measures implemented by the RFO concerning GE (e.g. measures regarding maternity leave)
V7	GEP in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V8	GE strategy in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V9	International declarations on reforming research assessment signed & in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	e. g. DORA declaration, <u>reform of research assessment</u> ,
V10	Other strategic GE policies in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	This may concern, for example, other mission or vision policies, statements of the RFO, where GE or diversity issues also play a considerable role
V11	Formal job position for GE issues in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	At least 50 % of full-time equivalent position
V12	Monitoring of GE in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Minimum: Collection and publishing of sex-disaggregated data on applicants and/or grantees
V13	Gender capacity-building measures for panel members in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Different formats of mandatory or voluntary GE training in place (e.g. video on GE)
V14	Gender capacity-building measures for remote reviewers in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know 4 = There are no remote/external reviewers in place, thus GE capacity-building measures for remote reviewers are not needed	Different formats of mandatory or voluntary GE training in place (e.g. video on GE)
V15	Gender capacity-building measures for staff in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Different formats of mandatory or voluntary GE training in place (e.g. video on GE)
V16	Gender capacity-building measures for RFO management in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Different formats of mandatory or voluntary GE training in place (e.g. video on GE)
V17	Maternity leave measures in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V18	Parental, paternity leave measure in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	

V19	Industry leave measures in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V20	Sick and/or care leave measures in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V21	GIR as assessment criterion in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Gender-in-research (GIR)
V22	Final gender re-ranking measure in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Re-ranking may have different faces (e.g. tie-breaking, quota): * equal to share of female applicants * equal to share of male grantees * prioritised within a defined frame/band * calibrated across fields or years
V23	Other GE measures (not mentioned above) in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	e. g. specific workshops for potential female applicants
Variables targeting the panel level of the funding programme under consideration			
V24	Formalised rules for selection of panel members in place	1= Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V25	Number of total panel members (incl. chair and vice-chair)	Numeric variable	
V26	Number of male panel members (incl. chair and vice-chair)	Numeric variable	
V27	Number of female panel members (incl. chair and vice-chair)	Numeric variable	
V28	Panel chair by sex	1 = Male panel chair 2 = Female panel chair 3 = Not applicable (other sex, information not available)	
V29	Panel vice-chair by sex	1 = Male panel vice-chair 2 = Female panel vice-chair 3 = Not applicable (other sex, information not available) 4 = The position of vice-chair does not exist	
V30	Information on nationality of panellists available	1 = Yes 2 = No	
V31	Number of national panellists	Numeric variable	
V32	Number of panellists with nationality from neighbouring countries	Numeric variable	
V33	Number of panellists with nationality from other European countries (but not neighbouring countries)	Numeric variable	
V34	Number of panellists with nationality from non-European countries	Numeric variable	

V35	Number of panellists for whom information on nationality is not available	Numeric variable	
V36	Information on location of home institution of panellists available	1 = Yes 2 = No	
V37	Number of panellists working at institutions located in the RFO's country	Numeric variable	
V38	Number of panellists working at institutions located in neighbouring countries of the RFO	Numeric variable	
V39	Number of panellists working at institutions located in other European countries (but not neighbouring countries and not RFO's country)	Numeric variable	
V40	Number of panellists working at institutions located in non-European countries	Numeric variable	
V41	Number of panellists for whom information on the location of the institution is not available	Numeric variable	
V42	Information on the institutional type of the home institution of panellists available	1 = Yes 2 = No	
V43	Number of panellists working at universities	Numeric variable	
V44	Number of panellists working at non-university research institutions (public or private)	Numeric variable	
V45	Number of panellists working in industry	Numeric variable	
V46	Number of panellists for whom information on institutional type of the home institution is not available	Numeric variable	
V47	Scientific discipline of panel	Text	
V48	Publication of panellists' names on RFO homepage	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V49	Panel format for observed call of funding programme	1 = virtual/online 2 = face-to-face/on-site 3 = hybrid 4 = Do not know	
V50	Formal process observers present at panel meetings	1 = Yes, RFO staff members are present and intervene 2 = Yes, RFO staff members are present, but do not intervene 3 = Yes, other external formal process	

		observers are present and intervene 4 = Yes, other external formal process observers are present, but do not intervene 5 = No, formal process observers are not present 5 = Do not know	
V51	Gender observers present at panel meetings	1 = Yes, gender observers are present and intervene 2 = Yes, gender observers are present, but do not intervene 3 = No, gender observers are not present 4 = Do not know	
V52	Does the panel report and discuss reviews of peer reviewer?	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V53	Does the panel discuss applications?	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V54	Responsible body for final funding decision	1 = Panel 2 = Body from RFO (e.g. board) 3 = Other body outside the RFO 4 = Do not know	
V55	Outcome of the panel meeting	1 = final funding decision 2 = funding suggestion 3 = other outcome 4 = Do not know	
V56	Assessment criteria are formally elaborated	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	With (clear) explanation; sub-questions which support the assessment
V57	Scores of assessment criteria are formally elaborated	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V58	Time use regulation per proposal in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	Each proposal is presented/discussed within a fixed time window (e.g. presentation + discussion time per proposal 10 min)
V59	Formal and clear rules for Col in place	1 = Yes 2 = No 3 = Do not know	
V60	When is Col checked?	1 = before panel meeting 2 = during panel meeting 3 = Not clear 4 = Do not know	

Source: own table

Part B of D6.1:

Gender bias in research funding evaluation: An experimental approach in a RFO

Name	Organisation	Contribution
Laura Cruz-Castro	CSIC	Main author 1
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